

D5.2. COUNTRY IMPLEMENTATION PLANS

WP5

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¹ PU = Public
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D5.2. Country implementation plans

Table of contents

GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS	4
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
2. PURPOSE and OBJECTIVES.....	9
3. METHODOLOGY	9
4. RESULTS	18
4.1. Eligibility criteria for admission of participants in the C4D programme.....	19
4.2. Professionals required for the delivery of the C4D programme	21
4.3. Recruitment phase of the C4D programme	29
4.4. Training of professionals	36
4.5. Materials.....	37
4.6. Online and face-to-face interventions	37
4.7. Digital platforms: training and monitoring of participants	38
4.8. Data collection	41
4.8. Aftercare phase	43
4.9. Sustainability actions.....	44
5. CONCLUSIONS.....	45
6. REFERENCES.....	47
7. ANNEXES.....	48
<i>Annex I. Template used for gathering data of the country-specific implementation plans</i>	<i>48</i>
<i>Annex II. Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) or Deming systematic process method</i>	<i>71</i>
<i>Annex III. SQUIRE.....</i>	<i>74</i>
<i>Annex IV. Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research Constructs (CFIR)</i>	<i>79</i>

GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

Term	Definition
C4D team	It is the core team of C4D JA in collaborative learning and knowledge generation which eliminates bottlenecks during the implementation of C4D practice, provides strategic vision and supports implementation process through the focus of the system, sustainability, scalability of the practice.
CFIR	Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research. The CFIR is a supportive tool on designing implementation plans to promote implementation theory development and verification about what works where and why across multiple contexts.
Grant Agreement	Funding agreement concluded between the European Commission/ funding agency and the project participants, which specifies the rights and obligations of the contracting parties.
Implementing countries	12 EU countries (Bulgaria, Belgium, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain), implementing C4D practice.
JADECARE	The Joint Action (JA) on implementation of digitally enabled integrated person-centred care (JADECARE) is an initiative to reinforce the capacity of health authorities to successfully address important aspects of health system transformation, in particular the transition to digitally enabled, integrated, person-centred care in the EU.
Key Performance Indicator	Critical (key) quantifiable indicators of progress toward the intended results.
Modalities	C4D JA will be developed over 12 months with T2D participants enrolled on face-to-face activities or online mode.
Phase 1 / Phase 2	Refers to the 6-month intensive care (Phase 1) and 6-month aftercare (Phase 2) intervention.
Pilot Coordinator	Person in charge of coordinating the multidisciplinary team in a particular implementation site.
Pilot implementers	They are engaged in the transfer and implementation of the best practice in implementing countries.
Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycle	It is an iterative, four-stage model used for improving a process or carrying out change, by guiding the thinking process into breaking down the task into steps and then evaluating the outcome, improving on it, and testing again.
Program Coordinator	Reference person responsible of the development of the VL BP for each participant.
Round A / Round B	It refers to the two consecutive groups of T2D patients taking part in the intervention, Round A starting at M12 and Round B at M21.
SCIROCCO	The SCIROCCO self-assessment tool is an online self- assessment tool with an objective to assess a region's readiness for integrated care. It builds on the conceptual Maturity Model for Integrated Care developed by the B3 Action Group on Integrated Care of the European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing.

SQUIRE 2.0	The SQUIRE guidelines provide a framework for reporting new knowledge about how to improve healthcare.
Stages	They include the Preparatory Actions already performed (In depth review of the BP and context reviews described in D5.1), Implementation and Post-implementation actions.
Steering Committee	It is responsible for the control of the progress and achievement of the project's objectives and for the prompt communication among partners in case something is delayed or needs to be discussed.
SWOT	SWOT is a technique for assessing four aspects: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. SWOT Analysis is a tool that can help analyze what your organization does best now, and to devise a successful strategy for the future.
VL best practice	The best practice selected for this JA is the "Reverse Diabetes2 Now experience" (RD2N). It is an evidence-based and reimbursed Dutch lifestyle treatment and training programme for type 2 diabetes, developed and promoted by the Dutch non-profit organisation Voeding Leeft.
Acronym	Description
BE	Beneficiary Entity
BP	Best Practice
C4D	CARE4DIABETES: Reducing the burden of non-communicable diseases by providing a multi-disciplinary lifestyle treatment intervention for type 2 diabetes
CFIR	Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research
D	Deliverable
F2F	Face-to-face
GA	Grant Agreement
GP	General Practitioner
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IT	Information technology
JA	Joint Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month, calculated from the start of the project (M1=February 2023)
MDT	Multidisciplinary Team
NA	Not Applicable
PDSA	Plan-Do-Study-Act
RD2N	Reverse Diabetes 2 Now
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
TtT	Training the Trainers
T2D	Type 2 diabetes
VL	Voeding Leeft
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the second deliverable of the work package 5 (WP5) “Preparatory Actions”. This deliverable integrates information related to task 5.2 “Development of country implementation plans” and task 5.4 “Recruitment strategies design”, developed between month M4 and M9 of the project, as described in the Grant Agreement (GA) of the Joint Action CARE4DIABETES (C4D JA).

The C4D JA supports 12 Member States in reducing the burden of type 2 diabetes (T2D) through effective lifestyle treatment programs. Partners will implement a Dutch evidence-based best practice (BP) “Reverse Diabetes 2 Now” (RD2N), developed by the non-governmental organisation Voeding Liefert (VL). The specific objectives of the pilot intervention phase are:

- ✓ To enhance lifestyle counselling knowledge and skills among healthcare professionals involved in the project pilots.
- ✓ To transfer, pilot, evaluate and adjust a lifestyle intervention model for T2D patients in each implementing country.
- ✓ To improve lifestyle, quality of life and levels of glycaemic control and reduction in use of glucose-lowering medication among T2D participants.
- ✓ To integrate the lifestyle intervention model for T2D patients into local/regional/national health care services.

The **purpose** of the document is to summarise the C4D the implementing partner’s plans in 12 different countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain), and detail how they plan to deliver the VL BP in an integrated and sustainable way within each particular context.

The **objective** of this deliverable is to present an overview of the activities planned at national level for the intervention phase of the VL BP defining concrete actors (who), functions and roles (what), timeframe (when) and setting (where).

The **intended audience** are all members of the C4D consortium (competent authorities and affiliated entities), especially the WP leaders, C4D teams from implementing countries, and stakeholders involved in the pilot implementation and/or dissemination and scale-up of the VL BP.

The implementation methodology was developed based on proven techniques, specific procedures and recommendations oriented towards long lasting sustainability which were developed by the Joint Action on implementation of digitally enabled integrated

person-centred care (JADECARE), as determined in the GA of the C4D JA. The methodology is based on the use of **Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles (or Deming systematic process)** for continuous tracking and improvement, the **SQUIRE 2.0** framework for reporting new knowledge about how to improve healthcare, and the **Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)** for including elements that could influence on a positive or negative way the process of sustainability of the BP.

Other methods were included in the preparatory actions, such as the SCIROCCO self-assessment tool to understand RD2N, and the **Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT)** approach to analyse different contexts.

This document includes different stages: a set of preparatory actions already described in the deliverable D5.1 “In-depth review of BP and context analysis”, a stage of intervention, and a stage of post-intervention.

The present deliverable focuses on the practical preparation for the intervention stage and accounts for the information regarding “implementation plans” to reproduce the BP at local level.

It addresses cross-sectional elements that will be further reflected upon on different deliverables during the project life, such as: communication and dissemination activities (D2.3); data collection and management (D3.2), development of a digital platform (D5.3) and sustainability oriented actions (D4.1).

Considering the early time in the project in which the information regarding implementation plans was collected and highlighting the fact that 8 out of the 12 participating countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Malta, Poland, Portugal and Slovakia) had not yet been trained on the BP by VL through the *Training the Trainers*, certain degree of change is foreseen on the implementation plans on the following months after this deliverable is submitted up to the start of the pilots. In **conclusion**, this document defines the intended development of activities to implement the VL BP in each particular context taking a basic common framework and compares and analyses the results at regional/country level aiming sustainability beyond the end of the JA.

Subsequent alterations to the plan will be reflected in upcoming deliverables, such as D6.2, Intensive care implementation on monitoring and reporting (Phase I) and D3.2, Interim and final evaluation reports.

Progress: All countries filled in the required information on the implementation plan templates with different degrees of detail, corresponding to the readiness to decide some of the specifics at such early stage and their different levels of knowledge of the BP. The preparation for this deliverable was set at the start of T5.2 and T5.4 (May, 2023)

whilst the country-level information was collected on M7 and M8 (July and August, 2023) and compiled in this document by M9 (September, 2023).

2. PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES

The purpose of this deliverable is to summarise the implementation plans of the C4D participants located in 12 different countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain). The implementation plans describe how the Dutch evidence-based BP RD2N, developed by the non-governmental organisation VL will be delivered and integrated in the different countries/regions for guiding the successful implementation and future sustainability. This information will be essential for the competent authorities and affiliated entities participating in C4D, WP leaders, C4D teams implementing the BP, and stakeholders involved in the pilot implementation and/or dissemination and scale-up of the BP.

The objective of this report is to present an overview of the foreseen activities during the intervention phase of C4D starting in January 2024, defining concrete actors (who), responsibilities and roles (what), timeframe (when) and setting (where) at country level.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology has been designed to compile the required information from the different partners describing their initial intervention intentions (methodological approach). It is based on several scientific theories and approaches applied during different stages of the implementation plan for delivering the VL BP (methodological framework).

3.1 Methodological approach

Considering the common aspects that all pilot implementers partners must foresee beforehand, templates for the planned activities during the implementation phase were designed and distributed. They provided a common structure and guidelines for all partners in order to prevent missing relevant elements that need to be considered.

The templates used for collecting data are presented in Annex I. These were shared with instructions and recommendations on how to complete them. This information has been collected for a period of approximately two months. A summary of the content of the templates is described below.

Structure of the Implementation Plan templates	
Phase I: Intensive Phase template	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multidisciplinary team, including roles description and recruitment of personnel involved. - Participants recruitment, eligibility criteria (inclusion-exclusion criteria), number of participants, where (recruitment site), what (materials) and who (people involved), referral pathway (intensive phase), consent form, preintervention data collection and recruitment flowchart. - Digital platform and related actions. - Other preparatory actions. 	
Phase II: Aftercare template	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Referral pathway for aftercare phase. - Pilot actions aftercare. 	

Partners participating in the implementation activities for the 12 countries are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. Countries and partners participating in the implementation activities

Country	Name of institution	Acronym
Spain	Consejería de Salud del Principado de Asturias Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias Fundación para el Fomento en Asturias de la Investigación Científica Aplicada y la Tecnología	CSPA SESPA FICYT
	Servicio Cántabro de Salud Fundación Instituto de Investigación Marqués de Valdecilla	SCS IDIVAL
	Servicio Gallego de Salud	SER GAS
	Junta de Extremadura Fundación para la Formación e Investigación de los Profesionales de la Salud de Extremadura	JUNTAEX FUNDESALUD
	Servicio Andaluz de Salud Fundación Pública Andaluza Progreso y Salud	SAS FPS
	Fundación Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria de Aragón	GAIAP
	Belgium	SCIENSANO
Bulgaria	Ministerstvo na Zdraveopazvaneto	MoH BG
	Regional Health Inspection Blagoevgrad	RHI
Finland	Terveysten ja Hyvinvoinnin Laitos	THL
	Finnish Diabetes Association	FDA
Greece	1st Ygeionomiki Perifereia Dype Attikis	1ST YPE
	General Hospital Elena Venizelou – Alexandra	ALEXANDRA
Hungary	Nemzeti Népegészségügyi Központ	NPHC
Italy	L'Istituto Superiore di Sanità	ISS
	Azienda Sanitaria Locale Roma 2	ASL ROMA 2
	Findazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli	FPG

	Azienda Ospedaliero Universitaria Pisana	AOUP
Malta	Ministry for Health – Government of Malta	MFH
Poland	Narodowy Fundusz Zdrowia	NFZ
	Warszawski Uniwersytet Medyczny	MUW
Portugal	Ministerio da Saude – Republica Portuguesa	DGS
	Associação Protectora dos Diabéticos de Portugal	APDP
Slovakia	Ministerstvo zdravotníctva Slovenskej republiky	MoH SR
Slovenia	Nacionalni Inštitut za Javno Zdravje	NIJZ
	Splošna bolnišnica Novo Mesto	SB-NM

3.2 Methodological framework

The methodological framework describes the theories or methods that have inspired the different tools used in each moment of the Implementation plan, including those required during the preparatory actions, the intervention and post-intervention stages. They will be briefly described along this document and further details about each of them can be found in Annex I.

The methodology to be used during the intervention phase of the BP has been organized on “stages” according to the different steps required (Figure 1): all the preparatory actions that would lead to the timely intervention with people with T2D (preparatory actions), the intervention phase (Phase I) and a subsequent period to collect the lessons learned and evaluate the results (post-intervention phase-Phase II). These would guide Pilot Implementer’s actions taking into consideration its applicability per pilot, the availability of their resources and the timeframe of the project while ensuring its scientific soundness.

Figure 1. Implementation Stages in the C4D JA.

Stage 1: Preparatory actions

The challenge of transferring a particular contextualized successful practice into a different environment along the EU requires a deep knowledge on the original VL BP. But at the same time, the uniqueness of each particular context needs to be analysed to provide the best opportunity to transform that BP into a local real possibility. Different preparatory actions have been developed for the BP implementation.

These preparatory actions include a comprehensive analysis of the VL BP, general aspects to be considered by the local pilot teams when designing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating their C4D practices. They also examine the country-specific circumstances, including key stakeholders' identification, to involve them along the C4D pilot countries as facilitators of the entire process.

The deliverable D5.1 *Best practice and situation analysis*⁵, already described the preparatory actions prior to project implementation, includes an in-depth review of the VL BP and an analysis of the different contexts. Different methodologies were applied and described in D5.1:

- **SCIROCCO**, a self-assessment tool, used to identify the maturity of the health and social care systems, for the adoption and scaling up of integrated care, or best practice solutions.
- **Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)**, a construct to analyse determinants; it is designed to describe barriers and facilitators to implementation outcomes.
- **SQUIRE 2.0**, a framework for reporting new knowledge about the pilot actions and how to improve healthcare.
- **SWOT analysis**, a technique for assessing four aspects of the national/regional and local contexts, including stakeholders: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. It is a tool that can help to analyse what each partner does best now, and to devise a successful strategy for the future.

All the information collected in D5.1 sustains and grounds the Intervention and Post Intervention stages of C4D.

The deliverable D5.2 *Country Implementation Plans* will complement these preliminary actions by collecting important information on the initial design of each JA participant for implementing the BP in their country or local contexts. The **PDSA** or Deming systematic process method, provides an iterative testing of changes to improve quality of systems. This systematic approach has been considered as the basis for elaborating

⁵ Deliverable developed under WP5 by the NIJZ team June 2023. Not included in this document.

the templates that guide partners for the implementation of the VL BP in their countries (Annex I).

The deliverable D5.3⁶ *Guidelines for Online systems and platforms* developed by Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) provides guidance to design digital platforms for social interaction, monitoring of self-reported data and/or management of clinical data. The intervention must be accompanied and supported by a local digital community to ensure its success as many collaborative actions will occur *via* online.

Stage 2: Intervention

The objective of this stage, organized in different phases, is to present the process of transferring the VL BP. The intervention stage includes the participants' intervention with people with T2D and some of the activities required beforehand.

It describes the elements each strategy must follow in their particular country/area participating in the C4D JA. Detailed description is reflected to line up basic elements that all actors involved in the implementation stage must consider. It comprises the recruitment of participants and strategies to be used by health professionals that will conform multidisciplinary teams (MDT); the translation and adaptation of materials provided by the VL; the definition of online platforms planned to be used as part of the intervention online or other supporting tools for the face-to-face intervention; and the steps that will be followed during the intervention phase.

The intervention stage duration in C4D takes from January 2024 to September 2025.

Results will be monitored, collected, and evaluated, tracking participants with periodical clinical checks. The performance of the intervention will be assessed using the **PDSA methodology** to ensure quality standards.

Description of the intervention

This JA based on the transfer of the VL BP aims to provide people with T2D with skills for incorporating healthy habits into their lifestyles in a dynamic and experiential way (i.e., patients must 'live' and practice the concepts they are delivered during the sessions). These habits are based on 4 pillars: nutrition, physical activity, rest and relaxation (Figure 2).

⁶ Deliverable developed under WP5 by ISS team. July 2023. Not included in this document.

Figure 2. Pillars of the C4D BP.

The program will be developed along 12 months in 2 phases. The intensive phase consists in the creation of groups of people with T2D to participate in a Self-management Education and support intensive training for 6 months, and an aftercare intervention over the following 6 months to ensure that barriers are solved, and new habits gets sustainable over time.

During this time, theoretical content and practical activities about the 4 pillars of the BP (Figure 2) will be transmitted. Activities and workshops related to this content may include physical exercises, cooking, etc. Due to the behavioural changes expected from the start of the program, the first pharmacological reduction of antidiabetic agents will be carried out before the start of the intervention. Other modifications in medication will be made during the course of the program based on the biometric levels of the participants. This will be performed under strict (and continuous) medical supervision.

Two rounds of 2-phase interventions (phase I-intensive and phase II-aftercare) with a 6-month duration each are planned: the first round (**round A**) of Phase I aims to include a minimum 340 patients from the 12 pilot Member States. This round will start on M12 (January 2024). The outcomes will be assessed after application of the PDSA methodology for needed corrections and fine-tuning. The second round (**round B**) aims to involve a higher number of patients (minimum of 520) and will start in October 2024. The consortium will not apply the PDSA approach to the Phase II of the second intervention round (round B), due to time constraints of the duration of the JA. Each group will be organized into groups of 20 people approximately on face-to-face or online formats.

a) Face-to-face (F2F) refers to interventions that consist of group sessions over 12 months organized for the physical attendance of the participants. This modality will be supported by an online platform throughout the duration of the intervention and can include webinars and online sessions if that is deemed logistically appropriate for its correct development.

One overnight stay is recommended by BP owner in order to:

- Promote group bonding, through the joint acquisition of knowledge received and its practice.
- Focus. Extracting the participants from their own environment, responsibilities and situation at home.
- Assist monitoring. The stay would allow more control on following the program (less triggers in the program environment - as e.g., snacking).
- Safety. Participants would feel secure physically and emotionally (especially for patients with other medication than metformin).
- Unburden. The two starting days have a full schedule and are intensive. Some people would have to travel far to get to the location and it is not feasible to come and go two days in a row within the transport options.

As part of the PDSA cycle, locations selected for implementing F2F interventions will be continually assessed for improvement.

b) Online refers to interventions that consist of a programme carried out fully digital with no physical encounters, either at individual or group level. This modality will be also supported by an online platform throughout the duration of the intervention.

As part of the PDSA cycle, online platforms will be assessed for improvement.

c) Hybrid refers to interventions that will develop both a F2F as well as online interventions with different groups of participants.

Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA)

A first PDSA cycle is programmed for Intensive phase for round A, both over the F2F and, online formats. Phase I (intensive) is planned between January and June 2024. This will help to apply improvements on the intensive phase of round B (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Timeline for the intervention with Group A in C4D and first PDSA cycle.

A second PDSA cycle will take place in parallel with the aftercare phase (round A), also in both F2F and online interventions (Figure 4), to incorporate the necessary changes into round B. Phase II (aftercare) is planned between July and December 2024.

Figure 4. Timeline for the second PDSA cycle for group A.

The timeline for the third and last PDSA cycle after the intensive phase of round B -for both F2F and online participants- is shown in Figure 5. The intensive phase is planned between October 2024 and March 2025.

Figure 5. Timeline for the PDSA cycle for group B.

In summary, PDSA cycles will be applied to all phases with one exception: due to time constraints, it will not be performed during the aftercare intervention with round B participants.

Stage 3: Post-intervention

Once the intervention with people with T2D is completed, evaluation methods proven in previous European projects (**SQUIRE 2.0** and **CFIR tools**) will be applied.

Great part of the information feeding these tools will be extracted from the templates described above for collecting data on the implementation plans.

SQUIRE

The SQUIRE guidelines, published in 2008, are a set of 19 descriptive units that present how to examine and develop quality improvements in healthcare. The guidelines were developed over the years to respond to the insufficient and limited studies published in this field. They have proven to be useful for design and implementation, and for writing communications.

Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR)

The Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR) will examine factors influencing different levels of care delivery (patient care, delivery groups, health organisation or policy) that may have hindered or facilitated the implementation of the BP in C4D (Figure 6).

The CFIR offers some constructs that have proven effective during the implementation. It is adaptable to a variety of contexts and settings, and covers five key domains: the

intervention, the internal and external environment, the people involved, and the implementation process itself. Each domain comprises multiple constructs that interact in complex ways to influence the effectiveness of implementation.

CFIR would provide to the multidisciplinary pilot teams a specific methodology to identify relevant factors influencing implementation, increasing their potential success rate for future implementations.

The results of this analysis will be incorporated as a specific point within SQUIRE 2.0.

Figure 6. Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research (CFIR).

4. RESULTS

Pilot implementers have shared their prospective planification to implement the VL BP in their own context in order to provide equivalent benefits to people with T2D than those obtained in the Netherlands. The implementation plans of the BP have been outlined by each pilot country within their health, social and financial frameworks, taking into consideration the feasibility and sustainability of the pilot activities. This information has been compiled using the template detailed in Annex I.

The information gathered from the plans of the different countries has been integrated and discussed as part of this section. The calendar period to fill in the information by all implementing partners falls into summer period so the different teams had to make the internal meetings and arrangements coordinating over respective summer breaks, adding extra difficulties.

Despite those guidelines provided to all partners to help on defining their plans, different levels of BP knowledge (i.e., not all partners had already attended the VL sessions on the training of the BP - Training the trainers), large differences in the

implementation context, laws and regulations, and other unexpected differences could lead to the variability on the data collected.

There are still some missing or unknown data at the time of collection, and potential deviations from the initial planned activities may occur. The compilation resulted has to be considered as an initial “statement of intent” to guide the BP implementation, but changes in the initial plans may occur once the intervention activities of the BP are running.

4.1. Eligibility criteria for admission of participants in the C4D programme

The general eligibility criteria required for the admission of participants in the C4D intervention for the different Member States are:

- ✓ Age between 20 and 80 years
- ✓ T2D treated with medication (oral or injected medicines or insulin)
- ✓ Affected by T2D for a period between 1 and 10 years
- ✓ BMI between 25 and 40 kg/m²
- ✓ No COPD or kidney or heart failure diagnosis
- ✓ No bariatric surgery (own report/medical record)
- ✓ No eating disorder (own report/medical record)
- ✓ No pregnancy (own report/medical record)
- ✓ Committed to make lifestyle changes to control diabetes
- ✓ Ability to use digital devices
- ✓ Access to internet
- ✓ Sufficient language skills to take part in the program
- ✓ Possibility to take part in the program as provided (schedule, location)
- ✓ Willingness to measure blood glucose at home

Due to the variability in the health and social systems, the legal frameworks and cultural aspects of the Member States involved, deviations from the common eligibility criteria have been defined for specific countries.

Table 2 shows the deviations from the general eligibility criteria defined per country. These include BMI and medication of the participants, range of age and the period of use of medication, among others. Additionally, new criteria have been defined, such as concretion on the definition of kidney failure, planning pregnancy or special dietetic requirements (e.g., vegan), etc.

Table 2. Deviations at country level for the eligibility criteria for the implementation of the BP.

Country	Deviations	Comments
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Belgium	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To have diagnosed T2D no more than 6 years 2. Presently using medication but not treated with SGLT-2 inhibitors and GLP-Ras. 3. Being between 25 to 75 years old. 4. Kidney failure defined as eGFR < or equal 45 ml/min 5. Being pregnant or planning for pregnancy. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In order to adapt the pilot to the national initiative 'start trajectory' that will be launched in November 2023 to address patients with type 2 diabetes, Belgium will consider newly diagnosed patients and shorten the duration gap included in the study. 2. Due to its cardio-renal protective effect 4. No safety concerns if patient in good health and higher eGFR 5. If pregnancy is planned and occurs in the duration of the intervention, participant will not be able to continue in the study.
Bulgaria	In accordance with the provisions of Ordinance No. 8 of November 3, 2016, preventive examinations and dispensation of the Ministry of Health will be performed.	
Finland	N/A	N/A
Greece	N/A	N/A
Hungary	N/A	N/A
Italy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being between 40 to 70 years old 2. Body Mass Index (BMI) between 25 and 35 kg/m². 3. Ability to use digital devices and to have access to a PC or notebook. 4. Kidney failure with eGFR < 30 ml/min for 1.73m² or heart failure with critical CV and/or hypertension. 5. Suffering from serious depression. 6. Having an active event of plantar ulcers within the previous 3 months. 7. Suffering from serious diabetic retinopathy. 8. Suffering serious mobility impairment. 9. Suffering from other serious comorbidities. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Safety and feasibility reasons. 2. Safety and feasibility reasons. 3. Ensure they own or have access to the required technology. 4. Further definition of kidney failure.
Malta	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Presently using medication but not insulin or SGLT-2 inhibitors that should not/can not be stopped. 2. Ability to use digital devices and not illiterate. 3. Vegan. 4. Being pregnant or planning for pregnancy. 5. Individuals who are not Maltese nationals. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Safety concerns. 3. recipes provided are based on the Mediterranean diet and not specifically for those who follow a vegan diet. 5. In view of the culinary traditions we have, whereby the recipes will be adapted based on them.
Poland	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being between 20 to 70 years of age 2. Patients must have started GLP-1 RAs therapy at least 6 months before the start of the intervention. 3. Kidney failure defined with eGFR < 30 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To ensure digital literacy 2. To avoid bias on results regarding changes in body mass. 3. Further definition of kidney failure
Portugal	N/A	N/A
Slovakia	N/A	N/A
Slovenia	T2D patients using insulin – these will not be included. Potentially, they will be included in Group B.	Patients using insulin in general have far more experiences with self-measurement of blood glucose in comparison to patients who are not on insulin, therefore a discrepancy in knowledge might lower self-confidence of the latter group. However,

		based on experiences with Group A, patients using insulin might be included in Group B, if agreed with the pilot team.
Spain	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patients must have started any diabetes therapy at least 3 or 6 months before the start of the intervention 6 months. 2. Body Mass Index (BMI) between 25 and 35 kg/m² 3. Kidney failure defined as requiring renal replacement therapy for exclusion. Inclusion of patients with nephropathy. 4. Not having substance addiction and/or behavioural disorders 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To prevent bias due to the recent initiation of medications (6 months will be applied for GLP-1 RA and SGLT-2 inhibitors and 3 months for the rest of antihyperglycaemic agents). 2. To avoid participants with morbid obesity due to higher motor and metabolic complexity. 3. To provide a clear definition of 'kidney failure' <p>*Additional eligibility criteria included for intervention performed by SERGAS (Spain).</p>

N/A: not applicable.

4.2. Professionals required for the delivery of the C4D program

An engaged and committed MDT is the key driving force for the successful transfer and implementation of the BP. Each pilot site will need to identify personnel that assume the core competencies described by the four roles established by the BP owner: **nutritionist, nurse/general practitioner (GP), coach, and program coordinator**. The professional background might differ according to country *curricula*, but their performance will be alike.

Local teams, transferring and implementing the pilot actions, will receive training to adopt specific competencies required for delivering the programme, having in mind the existing local capacities and skills. When needed, healthcare staff can become trainers themselves, training and supporting further personnel that might be needed for the implementation of the BP at a local/regional level. Training to support participants once the intervention is finished will be also provided by the owner of the BP.

Permission to participate in the 2 rounds of the intervention programme will be handled as required by each country. Most countries will deploy regular personnel that will acquire new skills and tasks for the implementation of the programme.

4.2.1. Nutritionist

Nutritionists aim to transfer knowledge regarding adequate nutrition in the management of T2D and help participants to build healthier cooking and eating habits. Their responsibilities for the implementation of the BP are described below.

Responsibilities of the nutritionist

- Explain the metabolic disturbance of type 2 diabetes (insulin resistance).
- Guide participants in changing eating habits.
- Guide participants in nutrition-related activities (i.e., food shopping, cooking, recipes).
- Monitor participants progress and anthropometric data.

*Other responsibilities are:

- Provide individual consultations with participants.
- Support digital platform activities.
- Provide with motivation and resilience strategies.

*These might not be included by all pilot members

A registered dietitian will assume this role in most intervention sites within the JA (Table 3). In Spain, except for the region of Galicia covered by SERGAS, diabetes specialist nurses as well as primary care nurses with specialist knowledge in nutrition in the management of T2D will undertake these tasks due to no dietitians being routinely employed within their local health systems. In Bulgaria, these professionals will be externally selected by interview.

Table 3. Profile of the different participants in the implementation for the different countries.

Country	Job profile	Estimated time (hours)
Belgium	Dietitian	69
Bulgaria	Not reported	65
Finland	Dietitian (ad hoc recruitment)	100
Greece	Dietitian	65
Hungary	Dietitian	68
Italy	Dietitian	At least 3 hours/week
Malta	Dietitian	65
Poland	Dietitian	To be defined
Portugal	Dietitian	65
Slovakia	Nutritionist	210
Slovenia	Registered nurse certified for diabetes education	50
Spain	Diabetes specialist nurse, diabetes advance practice nurse, dietitian, primary care nurse	52 (To be defined by: GAIAP, JUNTAEX, SAS)

An average of 67 hours of dedication is estimated to be needed to cover this profile (Table 3), ranging from 50 to 100 hours. These values do not include data for Italy and Poland because of a different description of estimated hours and lack of data, respectively. In Slovakia, the number of hours exceeds the estimation by the rest of the countries due to the implication of the intervention team in all preparatory actions.

4.2.2. Nurse/GP

The role described hereunder presented a great profile diversity. Nurses will be responsible for ensuring the safety of the participants in the program and supporting medication management, including reduction of antihyperglycemic agents. Their responsibilities are described below.

Responsibilities of the nurse/GP

- Some nurses and doctors will have interchangeable responsibilities:
- Support patient education.
- Perform biometric monitoring.
- Management of medication.
- Provide guidance of the process.

*Other responsibilities are:

- Participate in recruitment activities.
- Arrange individual consultations if needed.
- Communicate with participant's GP.

- Support the digital platform.

Some specialised clinicians will perform more defined roles depending on profile:

Nurse:

- Registration of data and participants.
- Support education in the topics covered by the BP.
- Monitor the status of the participants.

Diabetologist:

- Medical management.
- Reinforce education.

*Other responsibilities are:

- Participate in recruitment activities.
- Arrange individual consultations if needed.
- Communicate with participant's GP.
- Support the digital platform.
- Provide with motivation and resilience strategies.

*These might not be included by all pilot members.

Primary care nurses with experience in the management of patients with T2D, diabetes specialist nurses, GPs and/or diabetologists will assume this role in most pilot interventions (Table 4). In Bulgaria, these professionals will be externally selected by interview.

Among the 2 roles, some countries will confer interchangeable responsibilities to nurses and doctors, as it is the case of Spain, Bulgaria, Hungary and Portugal, whereas other countries, such as Greece, Slovakia, Poland and Malta will define a different set of responsibilities for nursing and medical staff.

In Finland, there will be 2 nurses with different responsibilities participating: one to collaborate in the transfer of knowledge and process guidance, and a second nurse to work on the recruitment process, data collection and contact with physician for medication management. In the Spanish region of Andalusia, a primary care pharmacist will support with guidance on reduction of medication. It is worth noting that in Greece, the diabetologist will also assume activities to guide behaviour change and overall overview of participants.

An average of 90 hours of dedication per professional is estimated to be needed, ranging from 40 to 150 hours for all the countries except for Slovakia. In this country, the number of hours exceeds the estimation by the rest of the countries due to the implication of the intervention team in all preparatory actions. We have excluded from the average calculations Italy, for providing a different description estimated hours and Poland for the lack of concretation at this stage.

It is worth noting that in Greece, the diabetologist will also assume activities to guide behaviour change and overall overview of participants.

Table 4. Description of the role of nurse/GP

Country	Job profile	Estimated time (hours)
Belgium	Diabetes specialist nurse	95
Bulgaria	Medical doctor/nurse (externally hired)	100 nurse 100 doctor
Finland	Diabetes specialist nurse/diabetologist	150 nurse 1 50 nurse 2
Greece	Diabetes specialist nurse/diabetologist	65 nurse 95 doctor
Hungary	Primary care nurse/GP	95
Italy	Diabetologist	At least 3 hours/week
Malta	Practice nurse/ Medical doctor	100 nurse 100 doctor
Poland	Diabetes specialist nurse/diabetologist/GP	To be defined
Portugal	Primary care nurse/GP	100
Slovakia	Diabetes specialist nurse/diabetologist	205 nurse 210 doctor
Slovenia	Manages selection of patients with support of Nurse and pharmacological therapy	40
Spain	Primary care nurse, diabetes specialist nurse /GP, junior physician/ Primary care pharmacist	77*

*Data for GIAP, JUNTAEX and SAS is pending to be defined.

4.2.3. Coach

The coach role will support the process of behavioural change and guide participants throughout the intervention. They will also teach meditation and relaxation techniques, as well as other coping strategies.

Responsibilities of the coach:

- Create a safe setting for the individual and the group.
- Enhance participants' understanding of the effects of relaxation and sleep in the management of type 2 diabetes.
- Activate and monitor group dynamics.
- Guide in awareness and behavioural change.
- Guide to activation and integration of sustainable behaviour.
- Teach and guide relaxation exercises.
- Provide with motivation and resilience strategies.

***Other responsibilities are:**

- Share motivational and inspiring posts, videos and quotes in Facebook group (Belgium).
- Support the digital platform.

*These might not be included by all pilot members

A high variety of academic and professional profiles are found across the different country sites for this role, including undergraduate psychologists, psychotherapists and therapists, nurses (mental health nurses and nurses with post-graduate training in psychology/coaching) and physicians (Table 5).

Portugal and 2 Spanish partners (SERGAS and CSPA-SESPA-FICYT) will include both a mental health nurse and a graduate in psychology.

Greece will not include a separate role of coach for sustainability reasons; it will be assumed by the diabetologist in their pilot site duties to support behaviour change and participants' process.

An average of 72 hours of dedication is estimated to be needed by the coach, ranging from 40 to 150, except for Slovakia. In Slovakia, the amount of hours exceeds the estimation by the rest of the countries due to the implication of the intervention team in all preparatory actions. We have excluded from the average calculations Italy, for providing a different description of estimated hours and Poland for the lack of concretation at this stage.

Table 5. Description of the coach profile.

Country	Job profile	Estimated time (hours)
Belgium	Patient education therapist	69
Bulgaria	Kinesitherapist	60
Finland	Public health nurse and health scientist)	150
Greece	diabetologist	95 (includes time dedicated to doctor role duties)
Hungary	Psychologist	68
Italy	Psychotherapist	At least 3 hours/week
Malta	Psychotherapist	60
Poland	Psychologist	To be defined
Portugal	Nurses (mental health specialists or trained in coaching/psychology) Psychologist	60
Slovakia	Psychologist	200
Slovenia	Registered nurses – diabetes educators.	40
Spain	Nurses (mental health specialists or trained in coaching/psychology), Psychologist, GP	46*

*Data for GIAP, JUNTAEX and SAS is pending to be defined.

4.2.4. Program coordinator

The program coordinator will ensure the correct development of the programme and the timely data collection. They will act as main communicators with the participants and will manage and coordinate the agenda and guide the overall process.

The program coordinator identified in each country will be trained to manage the Digital Platform. Alternatively, another person of the team should be identified and trained for the purpose.

Responsibilities of the program coordinator:

- Quality assurance.
- Practical organization of the programme.
- Communication with participants.
- Communicate with participant's main health professionals when/if necessary.
- Administration and process overview.
- Manage the online platform (uploading and updating content).

*Other responsibilities are:

- Contact participant's main health professionals when/if necessary.

- Annual reports (reflection and evaluation).
- Management of Facebook groups.

*These might not be included by all pilot members

A high variety of academic and professional profiles are found across the different country sites for this role, including nurses, physicians, health promoters, primary care coordinators, psychologists and multidisciplinary teams (Table 6).

An average of 69 hours of dedication is estimated to be needed, ranging from 10 to 92 hours, except for Slovakia. In Slovakia, the amount of hours exceeds the estimation by the rest of the countries due to the implication of the intervention team in all preparatory actions. We have excluded from the average calculations Italy, for providing a different description of estimated hours and Poland for the lack of concretation at this stage.

Table 6. Description of the program coordinator.

Country	Job profiles	Estimated hours
Belgium	Primary care coordinators	86
Bulgaria	Medical and socio-pedagogical education.	100
Finland	Public health nurse and health scientist	70
Greece	Medical doctor (endocrine specialist)	95
Hungary	Health promoter	88
Italy	Health coordinator	At least 6 hours/week
Malta	Nutritionist	48
Poland	Dietitian	To be defined
Portugal	Multidisciplinary team	50
Slovakia	Medical doctor (endocrine specialist)	420
Slovenia	Registered nurses – diabetes educators.	50
Spain	Nurse/ Medical doctor/ GP/ Technical Advisor of the Comprehensive Healthcare Plan for Diabetes (CHPD) of Andalusia/ Multidisciplinary team	38*

*Data for GIAP, JUNTAEX and SAS is pending to be defined.

4.2.5. Other roles

Some countries have included additional roles that are currently available within their local contexts and relevant to achieve a successful implementation of the BP. These include supervisors, physical activity instructors or coaches, podiatrists and IT experts.

- **Multidisciplinary team supervisor**

This role aims to overview the execution of the programme activities of the interventions implemented (F2F and/or online). It might also support the monitoring of the digital platform.

This role will be included for the implementation of the BP in Italy, with a dedication of 6h/week.

- **Physical activity instructor/coach**

The role of physical activity instructor aims to support and educate participants on physical activity on all interventions implemented (F2F and/or online). It might also support the management of the digital platform.

This role is expected to be used in the case of Italy (motor scientist, with a dedication of 3h/week) and in Malta (physical activity instructor, with a total dedication of 48h).

- **Podiatrist**

This role aims to ensure participants' foot care. It might also support the management of the digital platform.

This role will participate in the implementation of the BP in the case of Italy, with an estimated dedication of 3h/week.

- **Information and Communication Technology expert/digital platform coordinator**

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) experts have been described as relevant actors for the implementation in the case of Italy and Slovenia. It aims to ensure the correct and secure functioning and use of the digital platform on all interventions implemented (F2F and/or online). This role has a foreseen dedication of 6h/week for Italy and 20h for Slovenia.

4.3. Recruitment phase of the C4D programme

4.3.1. Recruitment strategies

4.3.1.1. Recruitment of professionals

A variety of professionals will be required for the successful implementation of the BP. The following paths have been reported to be used for engaging professionals that might also aid with the recruitment and follow up process of the different countries participating in the JA:

- Clinical sessions. These have been reported by Spain (CSPA-SESPA-FICYT, IDIVAL, JUNTAEX) and Poland.
- Contact with National institutions (e.g., the national center for public health and pharmacy and Hungarian Scientific Society for Occupational Health and Medicine in Hungary).
- Dissemination activities (e.g., newsletters, websites and events have been reported to be used by the project beneficiaries in Spain and Hungary, respectively).

4.3.1.2. Recruitment of participants in the programme

The recruitment of participants for round A is planned to take place between October 2023 and December 2023 for all the countries conforming the JA.

The number of participants to be recruited by each pilot member has been defined by the GA prior to the start of the C4D project. Table 7 summarizes the figures agreed per country.

Table 7. Number of participants aimed to be recruited by pilot country for every round.

Country	Round A	Round B	Online A	Online B	Total
Belgium	30	30	N/A	N/A	60
Bulgaria	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Finland	N/A	N/A	25	25	50
Greece	30	30	N/A	N/A	60
Hungary	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Italy	20	40	N/A	N/A	60
Malta	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Poland	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Portugal	40	40	10	10	100
Slovakia	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Slovenia	20	20	N/A	N/A	40
Spain	120	120	50	70	360
Total	360	380	85	105	930

N/A: not applicable.

Note: Belgium, Finland and Portugal have reported a higher number of patients aimed to be recruited than the number committed at the Grant Agreement. Note that these numbers are reported at the planning stage of the intervention and final figures will be reflected in D6.2 and D3.2.

Recruitment campaigns will be organized at different levels. While Primary Care Centres, representing the main point of care for the target population will be holding the majority of these activities across all countries in the JA, also diabetes specialist centres and endocrine units in hospitals will be reached in the search for potential participants.

Outside the healthcare setting, patient associations as well as digital channels or events (e.g., congresses and conferences) will be considered for message dissemination among the target population. Additional details on the channels/locations planned to be used by the different project participants can be found in Table 8.

The recruitment of participants will be performed through the following pathways:

- Primary care centres. Most participants are expected to be recruited by primary care clinicians by the majority of C4D country implementers.
- Hospitals. To a lesser extent, due to the usual background of the patients routinely seen in endocrine and metabolic units (patients with type 1 diabetes and highly complex multi-morbidity patients with type 2 diabetes), hospitals are also contemplated by some members of the JA as a potential recruitment source.
- Patients' associations. A smaller percentage of patients will be expected to reach intervention teams by own accord (self-referred) and through associations of people living with diabetes.
- Digital channels. The use of flyers, social media or other type of announcements to the general public will allow interested individuals to reach C4D teams who can further refer to the appropriate professional for inclusion assessment. In Italy, the digital platform will hold a public section with dissemination purposes.
- Events. Hungary's recruitment campaign is oriented to disseminate the message among doctors of different specialities in congresses and conferences so that they can select eligible participants from their diverse places of work. Similarly, a press conference to policy makers and diabetes societies is planned in Slovakia.

Table 8. Centres/channels used for the recruitment of T2D participants across the different countries.

Centre/channel	Actors	Country	Number of centres/channels aimed to reach
Diabetes specialist clinic/centre	Nurses Doctors	Bulgaria	Not reported
		Greece	1
		Italy	3
		Portugal	1
		Slovakia	1
		Slovenia	1
		Spain	4
Primary care centre	Nurses Doctors	Belgium	2
		Bulgaria	Not reported
		Finland	2
		Malta	1
		Poland	1
		Portugal	3
		Spain	2-5
Endocrine unit/ward in hospital	Nurses	Bulgaria	Not reported

	Doctors	Malta	1
		Portugal	1
		Spain	2
Patient association	C4D team	Spain	1
Digital channels	C4D team	Belgium	2
		Italy	1 (digital platform)
		Spain	3-4
Public transport	C4D team	Malta	1 (ferry); others as needed
Events (press conferences, congresses, conferences, etc.)	C4D team	Hungary	Not reported
		Slovakia	Not reported

Arrangements of materials to support the recruitment process will include: flyers, roll ups, newsletters and/or talks in healthcare centres and patient associations as well as digital dissemination (social media and other websites of interest) and direct discussions with clinicians.

Referral pathway for intensive phase

Once a participant is identified coordination teams will need to be notified, with the exception of Portugal, Finland, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, Slovenia and the Spanish region of Andalusia where participants will be pre-selected from their pilot pool of patients using their medical records. When a notification is needed, electronic notifications (email/digital platform) will be sent in the majority of countries. Softcopy referrals and direct applications by coordinators will be incorporated in Malta. Other C4D members, such as Belgium, will run the pilot in assigned primary care centres where the C4D nurses can be directly approached for participant referral.

Program and pilot coordinators in the different pilot countries will be responsible to oversee and monitor the recruitment process, as well as making the final decision regarding patient inclusion in the intervention in most countries, except in Finland, where this duty will be accounted to the diabetes nurse. In the event where it is unclear whether a participant meets the inclusion criteria, a consultation with a broader multidisciplinary team will be arranged and a decision will be taken by the following roles:

- **Belgium:** GP.
- **Bulgaria:** endocrinologist, psychologist and other specialists relevant to the case of discussion.
- **Finland:** diabetes nurses and multidisciplinary team.
- **Greece:** endocrine doctors, internal medicine doctors, diabetes specialist nurses and the pilot coordinator.
- **Hungary:** program coordinator and patient's usual GP.
- **Italy:** C4D coordinator and the whole multidisciplinary team.
- **Malta:** multidisciplinary team.
- **Poland:** GP and a diabetologist that are currently part of the multidisciplinary intervention team.
- **Portugal:** N/A.
- **Slovakia:** individual members of the multidisciplinary team supported by the program coordinator.
- **Slovenia:** multidisciplinary team led by medical doctor.
- **Spain:** The Spanish consortium formed by the 6 entities taken part in the JA (CSPA-SESPA-FICYT, SERGAS, SCS-IDIVAL, GAIAP, JUNTAEX-FUNDESALUD, SAS-FPS). This consortium, that involves the participation of endocrine doctors, general doctors, psychologists, researchers, primary care nurses, diabetes specialist nurses and program coordinators, will regularly meet along the duration of the project.

4.3.2. Recruitment procedure

Before initiating the intervention, participants must fulfil the correspondent documents supervised and on due time. Documents might include:

- Recruitment eligibility checklist that will help identifying participants.
- Informed participant sheet that will support discussion with participants.
- Consent form.
- Registration.
- Data collection forms.

- Commitment form. This might not be included by all pilot members.

An example of the process for identification and collection of data is shown below.

Example of patient recruitment pathway

Appointment 1:

- Identification (or assessment)
- Information to patients/signature of the consent form

Appointment 2:

- Data collection (registration if not done online/previous appointment)

-Commitment form, when applicable *Additional appointments:*

- Additional trainings (e.g., use of the digital platform)

Data collection will also be taken from participants' medical records. The roles assigned for checking the recruitment eligibility criteria, delivering the informed participant sheets and consent forms, registering data of the participants and completing the collection forms have been identified by the different pilot countries. Program coordinators, GP and primary care nurses, endocrine doctors or physicians and nutritionists will be in charge of these responsibilities.

Table 9 summarizes the responsibilities at country/regional level for performing the eligibility check, distributing and explaining the informed participant sheet and consent form, registering the form and collecting the participants' data.

Table 9. Roles responsible for the management of the different documents required.

Pilot site	Recruitment eligibility checklist	Informed participant sheet and consent form	Registration form	Data collection form
Belgium	Project coordinator	Nurse	Project coordinator	Patients (self-reported data) and nurses and dietitians (biometric data)
Bulgaria	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	Multidisciplinary team
Finland	Diabetes nurses	Diabetes nurses	Program coordinator (online)	Diabetes nurses
Greece	Medical doctor (from MDT)	Medical doctor (from MDT)	Medical doctor or nurse (from MDT)	Medical doctor or nurse (from MDT)
Hungary	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	Program coordinator
Italy	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	MDT member designated by program coordinator	MDT member designated by program coordinator
Malta	GP	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	GP
Poland	GP in primary care	Program coordinator	Program coordinator	Nurse
Portugal	Nurses and GP	Nurse and GP	Nurse and GP	Nurse
Slovakia	Nurse, physician and nutritionist	Nurse	Nurse, physician and nutritionist	Project coordinator
Slovenia	Medical doctor	Medical doctor	Program coordinator	Program coordinator
Spain	GP, endocrine doctor, primary care nurse, endocrine nurse, receptionist in hospital and primary care, program coordinator	GP, endocrine doctor, primary care nurse, endocrine nurse, nutritionist, coach, program coordinator	GP, endocrine doctor, primary care nurse, endocrine nurse, nutritionist, coach, program coordinator	GP, endocrine doctor, primary care nurse, endocrine nurse, coach, program coordinator

4.4. Training of professionals

To prepare JA MDT members, VL provides training on the RD2N program to several JA members. The training is given in English as the vehicle language of the project. Once completed, the trained members will be in charge of transmitting this information and methodology to the local multidisciplinary teams that will implement this good practice adapted to their own contexts.

In order to acquire knowledge about the VL BP and capacitate as implementers, up to 8-10 healthcare professionals per pilot country were selected to receive the train-the-trainers action from VL. The training is delivered online and is organized per country cluster. Following recommendations on VL, 4-5 countries will compose each cluster. The training includes transfer of knowledge by several experts' presentations and practical activities throughout 5 sessions along 7-9 weeks, depending on the cluster.

Three rounds of trainings have been organised for the different countries in collaboration with the owner of the BP. The training of trainers will take place between May 2023 and November 2023 (Table 10).

Table 10. Sessions planned/held for training of trainers in the RD2N Best practice for the different countries involved in C4D.

	Round 1	Round 2	Round 3
Countries	Slovenia Spain Italy Finland	Belgium Portugal Greece Poland	Slovakia Malta Bulgaria Hungary
Dates	10/05/2023- 28/06/2023	21/09/2023-23/11/2023	28/09/2023-30/11/2023

When required, the training will be replicated in each country's mother tongue to transfer the information of the VL BP among implementers that do not attend the original Training the Trainers (TtT) by the owner of the BP. This is the case of Spain, Greece, Italy and Portugal, where the intervention will be implemented at different locations requiring a greater number of MDT members than the ones trained in English. Malta expects to organize a training for prospective implementers for the second round. For this purpose, translation of VL materials will be enabled immediately after to facilitate *cascade* transmission of knowledge on BP.

4.5. Materials

Different types of materials will be necessary for the implementation of the programme, such as intervention materials for the delivery of the BP and additional physical materials for monitoring the status of the participants. Some of them were facilitated by VL before the TtT. Additionally, each partner might generate their own content adapted to their local context and needs in order to support a successful implementation of the BP.

Adaptation of materials for the delivery of the BP

All partners plan to translate and/or adapt materials from VL. These may include presentations, recipes, videos, books (electronic or printed) or others.

Additionally, most countries will also create culturally adapted recipes and elaborate their own materials to be used.

Any material from VL that requires printing will need to be reviewed and approved by them, as BP owners.

Materials for clinical monitoring of participants

Measurement tools that enable participants self-monitoring, as encouraged by the programme, that can include glucometers, scales, metric bands etc. will need to be ensured before the initiation of the intervention. Where a high number of participants is expected to own the required equipment, pilot teams will need to provide for those who do not have them. In that regard, some members of the JA are considering the possibility of arrangements with pharmaceutical companies, such as Belgium; equipment provision by diabetes centres, as mentioned by Greece, primary care centres, as it is the case with Italy, and patient associations, such as Finland.

Nevertheless, these arrangements will need to be defined by most partners at a later stage.

4.6. Online and face-to-face interventions

The program is planned to be developed as hybrid by two countries, Portugal and Spain. Finland will stick to their initial plan of “fully online” as Malta just “fully F2F”. The rest of the beneficiaries are planning F2F intervention of the BP. As a summary, the chosen format of the 12 countries participating in the implementation of the BP would be: 2 hybrids, 1 online and 9 F2F.

For those implementing F2F interventions, a suitable location that reunites the requirements to develop the intervention will need to be identified. The venues

described on the current plans vary depending on the plans of hosting or not a session that includes overnight stay and involves hotels and hostels, primary care centers, hospital units and facilities within national health authorities. When it is indicated, some parts of the program, such as routes to walk or relax, space to cook etc. will need to be planned considering the physical space of the chosen location. The chosen space will also need to meet technical requirements that enable the delivery of the sessions, such as electric plugs, possibility of using a projector/screen, appropriate furniture for the participant group and the correct display of materials etc. Also, transport to reach the chosen location and ensuring there is food/catering for the multidisciplinary team and the participants in line with the program will need to be defined.

Regarding the overnight coexistence experience just Malta, Poland, Slovakia and 4 affiliated entities from Spain are planning to implement it.. The rest allege locations, financial and logistic barriers that would prevent them to organize the overnight stay suggested by the VL BP.

Considering a liability insurance is also highly recommended for all the pilots.

It should be noted that, at the time of reporting this information, plans are at early stages of preparation and specific details are still in the process of discussion and definition by the different countries.

4.7. Digital platforms: training and monitoring of participants

Partners that will implement the BP either hybrid or fully digital will take care of identifying or developing an online intervention system/platform for the intensive programme. All partners will either establish or identify an online tool that will serve as the community platform for patients' interaction (e.g., Facebook).

Along with the sessions with the multidisciplinary team, patients will be invited to join an online peer-learning platform. This could be integrated into pre-existing online web pages or partners' platforms according to the number of patients involved and their needs, when applicable, and in line with national data protection rules.

Patients will be able to meet peers and interact with their local healthcare team. The platforms will be used to share opinions and experiences, recipes and suggestions to help with the adoption of healthier lifestyle by the pilot participants.

The setup and use of the digital platform should aim to reach concrete objectives adapted to the context of the country/area and related to the general KPIs of a digital tool (availability, resilience to out-of-service events, usability, portability, fruition ...), as

detailed in the deliverable D5.3. Partners will ensure compliance with their respective data protection laws.

The pilot member leader of the task 5.3 *Coordination and development of the online portal/intervention system*, ISS, has designed and developed the architecture of a Moodle digital platform that can be transferred to the different country members within the JA. These countries will need to translate it and adapt it for their own internal use following training provided by ISS.

Current plans regarding the digital platform include:

- Spain, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy, Malta, Poland and Portugal plan to benefit from the platform developed by ISS.
- Finland, Slovakia, Slovenia and Hungary expect to develop internally an online portal. Hungary's digital system that will be specifically created for the project aims to support only data collection.
- Belgium plans to use other platforms for community contact within participants (Facebook).

The platform will be fed by the multidisciplinary teams at different levels for:

1. Answering questions in the community and understand concerns.
2. Uploading information relevant to the programme: recorded sessions (webinars), blogs, activities, articles, participant experiences, etc.
3. Upload recipes adapted to national contexts.
4. Monitor participants' progress.

Additionally, data must be collected to support evaluation and to provide information to fine-tune architecture, contents and activities. The timely collection of the data supports the pilot implementers to correctly associate these actions to the other actions in their PDSA cycles.

Different actions will be needed for the release and use of the digital platforms to be running at national level. These include:

- The design and construction of the digital platform. ISS has designed the architecture of a national platform in a Moodle based environment. This will serve as a basis for other project participants.
- Preparation of the digital platform content. Materials (e.g., videos, photos), recipes, etc. will be designed/adapted following the approach of the VL BP.
- Preparation of a user's manual of the platform.

- Test and validation of the digital platform.
- Integration of improvements, finalization and release of the digital platform.

The digital platforms are expected to be released by January 2023.

The management and assessment of the digital platforms in the digital countries is foreseen to be performed mainly by the coordinators, but also ICT officers and/or nurses.

Table 11 shows the countries that are expected to use the ISS platform (Spain, Greece, Malta, Portugal and Poland) and those countries (Finland, Hungary and Slovakia) that expect to develop their own before the intervention.

Table 11. Internal organization of the different steps required to use the platforms by the JA participants.

Country	Design and construction of the Digital Platform architecture	Preparation of the digital platform content	Preparation of the platform users' manual	Test and validation of the digital platform
Belgium	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Bulgaria	ISS	RHI Blagoevgrad	ISS	ISS
Finland	Multidisciplinary team	Multidisciplinary team	Multidisciplinary team	Multidisciplinary team
Greece	ISS	Multidisciplinary team		ISS
Hungary*	IT department	Program coordinator, nurse, IT	Information technology (IT) department	*Digital platform will be created for data collection in Hungary. Community will be held via Facebook and session content delivered via Zoom
Italy	ISS	ISS	ISS	ISS
Malta	ISS	Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate	ISS (translated in English)	ISS for overall testing. Health Promotion and Disease Prevention Directorate for testing at national level
Poland	ISS	MUW	MUW	ISS for overall testing MUW for testing at national level
Portugal	ISS	APDP/DGS	APDP/DGS	ISS for overall testing APDP/DGS for testing at national level
Slovakia	Website developer	MoH SR	Developer contractor	Website developer in cooperation with MoH SR and members of the

				multidisciplinary team
Slovenia	C4D group Slovenia, IT staff at e-diabetes	Prelom, d.o.o. and Association of Nurses in endocrinology ⁷	Prelom, d.o.o. and Association of Nurses in endocrinology ⁷	Prelom, d.o.o. and Association of Nurses in endocrinology
Spain	ISS	Spanish consortium (CSPA-FICYT, SERGAS, SCS-IDIVAL, GAIAP, JUNTAEX-FUNDESALUD, FPS-SAS)	Spanish consortium (CSPA-FICYT, SERGAS, SCS-IDIVAL, GAIAP, JUNTAEX-FUNDESALUD, FPS-SAS)	ISS for overall testing CSPA/SESPA for testing at national level

N/A: not applicable. Digital solution for this pilot will be Whatsapp with the only purpose of social interaction.

4.8. Data collection

Data to support evaluation of the implementation will be collected using quantitative and qualitative methods defined by the leader of WP 3: evaluation. Simultaneously, the data collected will provide information to partners to fine-tune their activities. The timely collection and assessment of the data will support the pilot implementers in their PDSA methodology (see Annex II).

Data collected will assess:

- Benefits of intensive lifestyle interventions for patients with type 2 diabetes
- Cost-effectiveness, i.e., benefits for type 2 diabetes participants vs. the costs of the implementation
- Potential effect on type 2 diabetes burden for countries' health systems
- Sustainability potential:
 - success of dissemination to intended communities;
 - patients, health care personnel and stakeholders' satisfactions;
 - the effect of JA results to other EU Member States outside the partnership.
- Degree to which project results are non-dependent on fast changing factors (such as technology, economy, health situation).

Different sources will be used for monitoring and reporting such as: routine project statistics, management information, national or local health statistics, baseline-end line surveys, semi-structured interviews, focus groups, and observation.

Sets of data during the course of C4D JA will be collected at 4 levels (Figure 7):

⁷ Prelom d.o.o. is an organisation that is responsible for IT maintenance of e-diabetes.si site

- Participant level (clinical and behavioral outcomes, background characteristics and satisfaction). MDTs will be responsible for collecting data of participants in the program, that will be handled by pilot coordinators in most cases.
- Pilot site level (inputs, outputs, outcomes, PDSA, costs). Program and pilot coordinators and of the MDTs are the persons appointed for collecting and storing these data at each pilot site.
- Consortium level (outputs, outcomes, processes, etc.) Program coordinators will refer to the WP leader THL for further analysis at Consortium level.
- National&EU level (sustainability and transferability and cost effectiveness). As leader of WP4 (Sustainability), partner NIJZ will be responsible to ensure the development of plans for further uptake sustainability during the intervention. They will elaborate the project *lessons learnt* and draft statistical and health economic analysis, in collaboration with WP3 leader (THL). Economic impact assessment will be performed by THL, supported by the OECD team.

Figure 7. Levels of data collection and evaluation in C4D.

All information gathered and collected by the C4D partners will be organised and incorporated into the structure defined by SQUIRE 2.0. Additional information can be found in Annex III.

Additionally, through CFIR framework C4D researchers will select the constructs most applicable to our particular field of study, allowing a deep understanding of the implementation process and an analysis methodology, facilitating future deployment of

practices and tools. Additional information on the constructs and their definition is available in Annex IV.

4.8. Aftercare phase

The aftercare phase is a six-month consolidation period to ensure durable lifestyle changes by the participants after an initial six months of intensive care training. The C4D programme offers additional support to those that may need it, either with F2F reinforcing sessions or via online platform, promoted to stimulate the community support to grant a sustainable change over time. Monitoring and follow up of the general clinical status are also part of this phase.

The information to feed this deliverable was requested at a time when part of the partners did not receive the VL training yet and there are partial references. That could explain the variety and, in some cases, absence of response.

The continuation of the MDT delivering the intensive phase into the aftercare phase is intended by all partners, except Slovakia, where personnel has been recruited for the particular intervention –intensive and aftercare– purpose (outside their regular staff); in the rest of the consortium, the professionals involved are part of the current team and their initial commitment would mean for, at least, the duration of the participants intervention. Confirmation of continuity or correspondent replacement may be due, but always considering actual employees from their national systems. This method implies an approach for the sustainability of the BP after the end of the project.

Overall, the aftercare intervention is understood as a natural prolongation of the initial intensive intervention. Therefore, most of the information responds as a natural continuation aligned with previous intensive intervention.

In the cases where participants decide not to continue in the C4D programme, a withdrawal document will be offered by Greece, Spain, Malta.

Some partners, such as Hungary, consider the possibility of awarding a present to those completing the intensive phase before embarking onto the aftercare whereas other partners, as Malta, plan for a general meeting and a evaluation form taking place in between phases (M18).

In Greece, Poland and Spain, an informative letter about what to expect from the aftercare intervention has been described.

Frequency and format of follow up contact is discussed throughout implementers' plans. Generally, the the program coordinator at each pilot site would be the responsible to follow up. Hungary plans monthly follow up contact with participants and Malta intends

this follow up to take place by telephone contact. Slovenia plans to send reminders (date and time included in the medical report and individual SMS reminders to the participant one week before appointment) before the first session, and during aftercare. Italy is planning to request participants to contribute with topics of relevant interest for them, so that this can be included in the aftercare phase.

Where planned, F2F sessions in the aftercare phase will likely take place at the same locations as the F2F sessions carried out in the intensive phase, as long as positive feedback is received about it.

Online platform supervision and contents review are generally mentioned too in the different individual implementation plans, but without more specification due to the lack of knowledge at this current moment. All partners would proceed according to the needs detected alongside the progress and those detected after the PDSA cycles.

Data management and storage is a continuation from previous description during the intensive intervention. At participant level and pilot level data seems clear, but consortium level data needs to be defined. Finnish team, responsible of general evaluation of the C4D JA would provide further details to proceed under the same instructions.

Information included in this section must be considered as preliminary. The aftercare intervention information will be much more specific once the C4D JA intervention is initiated in January 2024.

4.9. SUSTAINABILITY ACTIONS

The implementation plan of the different countries has been designed considering actions that will ensure sustainability of the practice after C4D ends. Specific support will be provided to C4D teams while planning those actions by the leaders of WP4.

The elements that have been considered for the sustainability of the BP are:

- Involvement of staff from the **Regional Health System/Primary Care Centres** in the intervention (meetings, newsletter, websites, etc.).
- Maintain the **same MDT** for the implementation of the BP.
- Engagement of **policy makers** (regular meetings to incorporate suitable parts of the programme in the care practice) and integration on the National Health Authority policies or National Plans.
- Engagement of **stakeholders** (events, meetings, etc.); provide them with updated information on the topics of the BP.

- Create **national digital platforms** (if these are not available) and ensure the **availability of these and digital contents** once the projects end. In line with this, those partners using the materials of VL could be used after. Also, provide **funds** for keeping and updating the digital platforms and keeping updated the digital contents. Promote the BP through **dissemination activities**, including:
 - Congresses and conferences at national and international level.
 - Scientific publications.
 - Social media outreach (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram).
 - Press releases, press conferences and other events (e.g., World Diabetes Day, World Health Day, etc.).

5. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presents an overview of the activities planned at national level for the intervention phase of the VL BP defining concrete actors (who), functions and roles (what), timeframe (when) and setting (where). Data collected from the implementing partner's plans in 12 different countries (Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia and Spain) are compared and discussed within each particular context. Information on the recruitment of professionals and participants for implementing the C4D Programme, the roles required by the MDT involved in the delivery of the programme, the adaptation of materials and use of digital platforms at national level, the aftercare and sustainability actions are discussed in this deliverable at country level.

The expected outcome of this deliverable is to compile information regarding intervention planning as well as providing pilots with the necessary tools and defining arrangements required to successfully implement the BP locally, addressing important aspects to prevent missing relevant elements to successfully reproduce and sustain, according to each circumstance, the VL BP to meliorate the lives of people with T2D.

Pilot Implementer partners' plans are mostly aligned with the general common C4D patterns taking into consideration their internal particularities, such as their regulations and current protocols.

The information collected by all partners by using specifically designed templates to address important aspects of the intervention phase and aftercare activities has prevented that partners miss relevant elements for delivering the programme. After

their analysis, it can be concluded that the VL practices is better understood by all of them and that common elements at local level help supporting the successful implementation of the practice. However, it must be taken into account that not all partners have same knowledge level about the VL BP at the time of preparing the plan because some of them did not receive the training of VL on the BP at the same time and that the information displayed in this document dates from July and August, 2023, at a time when some of the specifics could need to be defined, therefore plans are foreseen to evolve up to the start of the pilots.

The context variability and the differences among implementing plans have led to justified adjustments to the different reported plans to be continuously monitored through the pilots meetings and the PDSA templates. Solid and definite information regarding the development of interventions at local level will be compiled in the D6.2, Intensive care implementation on monitoring and reporting (Phase I).

Partners reflect upon the sustainability of activities defined through their implementation plans and impacting directly on some of the decisions made. This could potentially lead to justified deviations that will be further described on upcoming documents (fidelity checklist, Do/Study/Act templates) and that provide inspiration and new scientific soundness for the reproduction of the BP and future related T2D actions.

6. REFERENCES

- SCIROCCO Methodology
<https://www.sciroccoexchange.com/uploads/SCIROCCO-Exchange-methodology-for-self-assessment-FINAL.pdf>
- CFIR Methodology <https://cfirguide.org/>
- JADECARE <https://www.jadecare.eu/>
- PDSA Model for Improvement <https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/qsir-pdsa-cycles-model-for-improvement.pdf>
- SQUIRE <http://www.squire-statement.org/>

7. ANNEXES

ANNEX I. TEMPLATE USED FOR GATHERING DATA OF THE COUNTRY SPECIFIC IMPLEMENTATION PLANS

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

STEP1-PLAN TEMPLATE

NAME OF C4D PARTNER WITH PILOT IMPLEMENTATION, supported by NAME OF C4D COMPETENT AUTHORITY

COUNTRY

Authors: Name1 Surname1, Name2 Surname2,xxx

Date: July 31 2023

Developed within Task 5.2 and Task 5.4, by CSPA-SESPA-FICYT:

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IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

This is a manual containing the elements each strategy must reflect in their particular country/area participating in the C4D Joint Action. Detailed description is reflected to line up basic elements everyone must consider.

It contemplates the PDSA Cycle (Step 1: Plan, step 2: Do, step 3: Study and step 4: Act) and the SQUIRE and CFIR methodologies that would be applied for analysis.

To guide your reading of the document, it is necessary to take into account the following definitions:

- Phase I - Intensive care implementation, capacity building oriented, 6 months duration.
- Phase II - After care, additional guidance and coaching, 6 months duration.
- Round A - First implementation program (includes Phase I and Phase II) with the first group of participants.
- Round B - Second implementation program (includes Phase I and Phase II) with the second group of participants.
- Modalities: online or face-to-face. 12 months duration in both cases.

The general Implementation Plan is structured in 4 steps (as in PDSA) and an additional point to remind the elements to consider in secondary and potential future implementation's rounds.

This document reflects STEP1.

First implementation plan for intensive phase and aftercare in C4D	
Date of the meeting (s)	Date 1, date 2...
Number and profile of the participants	C4D team members: organiser, experts, decision makers, multidisciplinary team members (nurse, dietician, medical doctor, coordinator, coach....)
Organizations involved	Organisation 1, organisation 2

Step 1 includes Phase I (Intensive care) and Phase II (Aftercare) and the general objectives are:

- To define C4D participants recruitment strategy.
- To define C4D multidisciplinary teams creation.
- To define C4D other preparatory activities, with specific focus to sustainability supporting activity (-ies).

PHASE I: INTENSIVE PHASE TEMPLATE

1.1 MULTIDISCIPLINARY TEAM

One key element of the implementation is the staff engaged and committed from early stages. The professional background might differ according to country *curricula*, but their performance will be alike. Each pilot site will identify and recruit personnel to develop the different roles described by the BP: Project Coordinator, Nurse/GP, Nutritionist and Coach.

Please note: It is strongly recommended that at least, the Project Coordinator would be trained to manage the DIGITAL PLATFORM. Alternatively, another person of the team should be identified and trained for the purpose.

ROLES DESCRIPTION

The different job descriptions will be described according to your profiles and distribution of duties.

Objectives:

- To describe roles of each professional at local level.
- To define professional commitments *per* role.

Notes for completion the table:

(1) Define the different roles needed for the delivery of the C4D programme planned in your country/area.

(2): Name responsibilities and tasks of each of the roles named in (1) like medication management, guides meditation, organizing and keeping agenda as planned, explains nutrition plan based on physiopathology of T2D, managing the DIGITAL PLATFORM, etc.

(3): Define the goals of each of the roles described in (1) like monitor blood glucose levels to ensure the safety of the programme or reducing medication, etc.

(4): Specify whether the role described in (1) will only participate in the face to face or the online programme or they will be present in both.

(5): Describe expected hours committed to every programme applicable by each of the roles in (1).

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Table 1- ROLES DESCRIPTION

Role (1)	Responsibilities and tasks (2)	Goals (3)	Format (4)	Estimated hours (5)
Nurse/GP (Role 1)				
Nutritionist (Role 2)				
Coach (Role 3)				
Project coordinator (Role 4)				

RECRUITMENT OF PERSONEL INVOLVED

Describe the profiles your context will be including to become the multidisciplinary team and what strategy of recruitment used: current personnel with new tasks or *ad hoc* recruitment. Keeping the principle of sustainability in mind can help maintain good practice once the project is completed (i.e.: experienced nurses working with diabetes patients, special diets connoisseur, will adopt the nutritionist role as National Health Plan does not include this role in Spain).

Objectives:

- Describe professional profiles or role at local level.
- To describe recruitment strategies.

Table 2- RECRUITMENT

Role	Description

PARTICIPANTS RECRUITMENT

This document contains information to support partner's local participants' recruitment.

It includes a timeline with key deadlines to fulfil, along with recruitment strategies adapted to different needs such as: call for interests, online announcements, direct contacts, commitment of patients' associations, pharmacies, centres for diabetes, and health insurance funds, engagement of general and specialist practitioners, organisation of in-person or online info days.

Each participating country/area will follow a methodology that is most feasible for them, in line with the national ethical regulations.

A recruitment strategy should include information on:

- Patient identification: inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Number of subjects: recruitment target.
- Plan for recruitment.
- Referral pathway.
- Preparatory activities prior to intervention.
- Participant flowchart.
- Forms used during recruitment process.

The following issues should be addressed with a level of detail appropriate to the project.

PATIENT IDENTIFICATION: INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

General criteria are established as per Grant Agreement and demographic conditions could influence too. In case of any deviation from common criteria, that should be clearly justified.

Inclusion criteria in C4D JA are:

- ✓ To have diagnosed type 2 diabetes for at least 1 year but no more than 10 years.
- ✓ Presently using medication (oral or injectable drugs or insulin) to treat T2D.
- ✓ Being between 20 and 80 years of age.
- ✓ Body Mass Index (BMI) between 25 and 40 kg/m².
- ✓ Committed to make lifestyle changes to control diabetes
- ✓ Ability to use digital devices
- ✓ Access to internet
- ✓ Sufficient language skills to take part in the program
- ✓ Possibility to take part in the program as provided (schedule, location)
- ✓ Willingness to measure blood glucose at home

Exclusion criteria in C4D JA are:

- ✓ Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD).
- ✓ Bariatric surgery.
- ✓ Kidney failure.
- ✓ Heart failure.
- ✓ Pregnancy (self-report).
- ✓ Eating disorders (self-reported diagnosis).

Notes for completion the table:

(1) Inclusion and exclusion criteria agreed by the JA (YES/NO)

(2): Add any addition and/or modification in your local country/area to inclusion and exclusion criteria and add any explanatory comments to justify this decision.

Table 3- PATIENT IDENTIFICATION: INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Country	Adopt inclusion and exclusion criteria (1)	Adapt &Comments (2)

NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS

This element will show the number of participants that you expect to recruit for the study, detailed in these objectives:

- To define the number of subjects that you expect to recruit at the different rounds of the study applicable in your country/area.
- To fulfil the key deadlines by which you plan to complete the recruitment process at the different rounds of the study applicable in your country/area.
- To define the total number of participants that you expect to recruit for the study.

Table 4- NUMBER OF PARTICIPANT SUBJECT

	Round A Face-to-face	Round B Face-to-face	Round A Online	Round B Online

Target number	X	X	X	X
Key deadline	Start: ddmmyyyy	Start: ddmmyyyy	Start: ddmmyyyy	Start: ddmmyyyy
	End: ddmmyyyy	End: ddmmyyyy	End: ddmmyyyy	End: ddmmyyyy
Total target number of patients recruited X				

RECRUITMENT SITE, MATERIALS AND PEOPLE INVOLVED

The main plan for recruitment in every country/area along with the key deadlines for each phase of the study relevant to each of the partners: where, what, who must be defined here.

Specific objectives are:

- To specify the location/s (physical or virtual) where you intend to display a recruitment campaign.
- To describe the different materials and strategies created to attract participants.
- To describe the health professionals involved specifying their practice scope (external or internal from the pilot team).

Notes for completion the table:

(1) Name the location/s (physical or virtual) where you intend to display a recruitment campaign (I.e. Primary care centre, etc.)

(2) Please, add brackets to indicate whether materials/strategies aim to recruit participants or health professionals that will aid to recruit participants; i.e. Flyers/posters (participants), Talks to clinical teams (health professionals), Internal newsletter (health professionals) etc.

(3) Describe actual activities to recruit participants (i.e. participant identified in clinic in primary care centre by primary care nurse).

(4) Describe performance measures, if applicable.

(5) Indicate how this activity is oriented to sustainability.

Activities	Actions	Actors	Timeline		Performance measures (4)		Sustainability (5)
			Start	Ends	Indicator	Target value	
Recruitment location/s (1)	<i>i.e. primary care centre</i>	<i>i.e. GP/primary care nurse</i>	<i>i.e. Oct 2023</i>	<i>i.e. Dec 2023</i>	<i>i.e. Number of primary care centres involved</i>	<i>i.e. 8</i>	<i>i.e. Involve teams from the national health system</i>

Recruitment strategies/materials (2)	<i>i.e. flyers</i>	<i>i.e. Reception teams in primary care centres and hospitals</i> <i>Pharmacy assistants</i>	<i>i.e. Oct 2023</i>	<i>i.e. Dec 2023</i>	<i>i.e. Number of flyers</i>	<i>i.e. 250</i>	<i>i.e. QR code leading to content of the flyer will be also displayed</i>

Participant recruitment (3)	<i>i.e. Patient identified in clinic</i>	<i>i.e. Nurse/GP/ endocrine specialist</i>	<i>i.e. Oct 2023</i>	<i>i.e. Dec 2023</i>	<i>i.e. number of patients recruited by this method</i>	<i>i.e. 20</i>	<i>i.e. Involve teams from the national health system</i>

Table 5- RECRUITMENT SITE, MATERIALS and PEOPLE INVOLVED

REFERRAL PATHWAY FOR INTENSIVE PHASE

Once the participant is eligible and will accept, there must be a pathway established to follow as a general procedure.

- Specific objectives:
 - To indicate referral format.
 - To define figure responsible for the final inclusion of the participant in the study.
 - To define action plan when it is unclear whether participant fulfils inclusion criteria.
 - To define figure responsible to overview the process of recruitment in your country/area.

Notes for completion the table:

- (1) Describe how pilot team will receive the referral: i.e., e-mail or form collection by allocated team member.
- (2) Indicate person/s responsible for final decision of inclusion of the participant in the study. (i.e. partner coordinator, GP...).
- (3) Indicate mitigations actions to define a plan in case of participant unclear fulfilment criteria, i.e. multidisciplinary team discussion (please, specify whether this decision will be made by the pilot team or you would consider discussions with external specialists).
- (4) Indicate most relevant figure responsible to overview the recruitment process in your country/area i.e., project coordinator.

Table 6- REFERRAL PATHWAY for INTENSIVE PHASE

1. Referral format (describe how pilot team will receive the referral)
2. Person/s responsible for final decision regarding patient inclusion in the intervention

3. In the event where inclusion of a participant is unclear, what steps will your country/area take?
4. Figure responsible to overview and monitor the recruitment process

CONSENT FORM AND PREINTERVENTION DATA COLLECTION

Before initiating the intervention, participants must fulfil their respective registration supervised and on due time.

Objectives:

- To define timelines for consent form signing.
- To define data that will be collected prior to the start of intervention along with timelines.
- To define the pilot members involved in the preparatory activities.

Notes for completion the table:

- (1) Name the activities needed to take up with participants in preparation to the intervention (signing Informed consent form, pre-intervention data collection, introductory training to the DIGITAL PLATFORM, others).
- (2) Indicate who is responsible for every activity described. Specify whether this is a member of the pilot team or an external health professional (primary care nurse, physician, other).
- (3) Indicate how (appointment, phone call, video call) every activity mentioned in (1) will be performed.
- (4) Indicate when (timelines) for the activities named in (1) (ie: appointment within 7 days from confirmation of inclusion criteria).
- (5) Describe here specific instructions to undertake for every activity. Add any other comments relevant to the activity (i.e.: participant will have the opportunity to address any queries/concerns about the intervention, i.e., data collection form will be handed to participant and measurements taken of: height and weight, BMI, waist circumference, etc.). Also explain data sources and quantitative and qualitative methods.

Table 7- CONSENT FORM and PREINTERVENTION DATA COLLECTION

Actions/activity (1) What data	Person responsible (2) Who	How (3)	Timeline (4) When	Comments (5)
Signing consent form and Informed Participant Sheet				
Pre-intervention data collection				
Recruitment form				
Registration form				
Others				

RECRUITMENT FLOWCHART

OPTIONAL: Visual summary will contribute to understand recruitment procedure and provide a summarized overview of the recruitment process with the most relevant information provided on previous tables.

Figure 1. Example of flowchart

THE DIGITAL PLATFORM: ASSOCIATED ACTIONS

Implementation plans must include an overview of the activities and related actions associated with the setup and use of the DIGITAL PLATFORM. These should aim to reach concrete objectives adapted to the context of the country/area and related to the general KPIs of a digital tool (availability, resilience to out-of-service events, usability, portability, fruition ...).

Additionally, data must be collected to support evaluation and to provide information to fine-tune architecture, contents and activities. The timely collection of the data supports the pilot implementers to correctly associate these actions to the other actions in their Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.

Main objectives of preparatory actions⁸:

- Design and construction of the Digital Platform Architecture.
- Preparation of the Digital Platform Contents.
- Preparation of Platform User Manual.
- Digital Platform Test and validation.
- Finalization and release of the Digital Platform.

Table 8- OVERALL ACTIONS FOR THE DIGITAL PLATFORM

	Activity (what :1)	Actors (who: 2)	Timeframe (when: 3)	Setting (where: 4)	Objectives (5)
1. CONSTRUCTION OF THE DIGITAL PLATFORM	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Design and construction of the Digital Platform Architecture.				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2- Preparation of the Digital Platform Content.				
	<i>i.e.</i> 3- Preparation of Platform Users' Manual.				
	<i>i.e.</i> 4- Test and validation of the Digital Platform.				
	<i>i.e.</i> 5- Finalization and release of the Digital Platform.				
	6- XXXX				
2. USE AND ASSESSMENT OF THE DIGITAL PLATFORM	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Management of the Digital Platform during Round A intensive phase				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2- Assessment of the Digital Platform performance and implementation of the needed corrective actions (Round A – STUDY and ACT; Round B - PLAN				
	<i>i.e.</i>				

⁸ They should be ready before the first ROUND will initiate in January 2024

	3- Management of Digital Platform during Round A aftercare phase and Round B intensive phase				
	i.e. 4- Final assessment and optimization of the Digital Platform (STUDY and ACT, after Round B intensive phase)				
	5- XXX				

OTHER PREPARATORY PILOT ACTIONS

Implementation plans must include an overview of the activities and related actions. These should aim to reach concrete objectives adapted to the context of the country/area and related to the general KPIs.

Additionally, data must be collected to support evaluation and to provide information to fine-tune the activities. The timely collection of the data supports the pilot implementers in their Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.

Objectives:

- To describe the activities required to implement the C4D intervention, defining concrete actors (who), functions and roles (what), timeframe (when) and setting (where).
- To define the objectives aimed by these activities and how they relate to the project KPIs

Notes for completion:

- (1) Enlist all the activities and related actions the C4D intervention requires that have not been already described within this document.
- (2): Name responsible for each activity in (1).
- (3): Indicate the duration of the activity (just once, over a month, undefined...), the *momentum* as part of the C4D Joint Action (M7, M8) and how long the activity takes to implement.
- (4): Describe the locations where the activity or action is planned like Primary Care department, office, hostel, private home, nursery, etc.
- (5): What do we expect to happen? Define the objectives of the activities.

(6): Sustainability Supporting Actions* -how C4D practice within each of the country could be grounded in (or would become during C4D), or be part of any systemic, system-wide, “bigger” framework, project, initiative, policy (I.e., National diabetes plans).

- who will be holding responsibility for sustainability of C4D practice after C4D ends
- do you have “the right” people, institutions, groups, networks on board – if not, links to be established.
- how good are you in communicating about your C4D practice plans and results, and in building up on collaboration with patients, professional networks and others
- how good is your internal and broader environment at adaptation, such as adaptive internal organisational structure with clearly defined roles and people (staff) engaged in the change process.

Question: Are you planning to organize the first two sessions including the overnight stay, for the group experience, as the BP owner recommends?

Y Yes

Y No

Table 9- OTHER PREPARATORY ACTIONS

	Activity (what :1)	Actors (who: 2)	Timeframe (when: 3)	Setting (where: 4)	Objectives (5)
1. INTERVENTION TEAM	<i>i.e.</i> 1. Prepare materials to train implementers				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2. Arrange training date and format				
	<i>i.e.</i> 3. Assess implementers and provide certificate upon completion				
	<i>i.e.</i> 4- Arrange contracts/retribution/permission for implementers				
	5-XXXX				
	6- XXXX				

2. INTERVENTION VENUE	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Book venue				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2- Arrange catering for participants				
	<i>i.e.</i> 3-Arrangement of demos and training for the online portal (during in-presence days)				
	4- XXX				
	5- XXX				
3. MATERIALS AND TOOLS (for participants)	<i>i.e.</i> 1-Create presentations				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2-Arrange measurement tools (i.e. glucometer)				
	<i>i.e.</i> 3-Define materials provided to participants				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
	2- Arrange member of the team to moderate platform				
	3- XXX				
	4- XXX				
4.SUSTAINABILITY SUPPORTING ACTIONS ⁽⁶⁾	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Involve staff from primary care centres to deliver the intervention				
	2- Invest in digital tools and online content				
	3-XXX				
	4-XXX				
	5- XXX				
5.DATA					

5.1 PARTICIPANT LEVEL DATA -Clinical and behavioural outcomes -Background characteristics -Satisfaction	1- Collect				
	2-Store				
	3-Evaluate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
5.2 PILOT LEVEL DATA -Inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes -Quality improvement -Costs	1-Collect				
	2- Store				
	3- Evaluate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
5.3- CONSORTIUM LEVEL DATA -Processes, outputs, outcomes -Satisfaction, quality improvement	1- Collect				
	2- Store				
	3- Evaluate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
6- DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Activities to promote participation/organization of the implementation				

PHASE II: AFTER CARE TEMPLATE

REFERRAL PATHWAY FOR AFTERCARE PHASE

When a participant moves onto the aftercare phase of the intervention, there must be a pathway considering this transition to follow as a general procedure.

- Specific objectives:
 - To indicate referral format.
 - To define action plan to support the transition of a participant to the aftercare phase.
 - To define figure responsible to overview the transition process in your country/area.

Table 10- REFERRAL PATHWAY FOR AFTERCARE

1. Referral format (how will the pilot team confirm whether a participant transitions to the aftercare phase?)
What other actions will be in place to support participant transition to the aftercare phase?

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3. Figure responsible to overview and monitor the transition process

MDT AFTERCARE DEDICATION

It is expected the same MDT team will continue the AfterCare part of the intervention. But the number of expected hours committed will be different. Please specify.

Role	Estimated hours

PILOTS ACTIONS AFTERCARE

An overview of the activities and related actions considering the aftercare phase must be defined. These should aim to reach concrete objectives adapted to the context of the country/area and related to the general KPIs.

Additionally, data must be collected to support evaluation and to provide information to fine-tune the activities. The timely collection of the data supports the pilot implementers in their Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles.

Objectives:

- To describe the activities required to implement the aftercare phase of the C4D intervention, defining concrete actors (who), functions and roles (what), timeframe (when) and setting (where).
- To define the objectives aimed by these activities and how they relate to the project KPIs

Notes for completion:

- (1) Enlist all the activities and related actions the aftercare phase of the C4D intervention.
- (2): Name responsible for each activity in (1).
- (3): Indicate the duration of the activity (just once, over a month, undefined...), the *momentum* as part of the C4D Joint Action (M7, M8) and how long the activity takes to implement.
- (4): Describe the locations where the activity or action is planned.
- (5): What do we expect to happen? Define the objectives of the activities.

Table 11- PILOTS ACTIONS AFTERCARE

	Activity (what :1)	Actors (who: 2)	Timeframe (when: 3)	Setting (where: 4)	Objectives (5)
1. INTERVENTION TEAM	<i>i.e.</i> 1. Select team involved in the aftercare phase				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2- Arrange contracts/retribution/permission				
	3- XXXX				
	4- XXXX				
	5-XXXX				
	6- XXXX				
2. INTERVENTION VENUE/ ONLINE PORTAL	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Define online platform used for aftercare purposes if eventual changes/adaptation would be required.				
	2- XXX				
	3- XXX				
	4- XXX				
3. MATERIALS AND TOOLS (for participants)	<i>i.e.</i> 1-Create follow up information books				
	<i>i.e.</i> 2-Arrange measurement tools (i.e. glucometer)				
	3-XXX				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
	2- Arrange member of the team to moderate platform				
	3- XXX				
	4- XXX				

4.SUSTAINABILITY SUPPORTING ACTIONS	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Involve staff from primary care centres to follow up participants				
	2- Invest in digital tools and online content				
	3-XXX				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
5.DATA					
5.1 PARTICIPANT LEVEL DATA -Clinical and behavioural outcomes -Background characteristics -Satisfaction	1- Collect				
	2-Store				
	3-Evaluate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
5.2 PILOT LEVEL DATA -Inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes -Quality improvement -Costs	1-Collect				
	2- Store				
	3- Evalate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
5.3- CONSORTIUM LEVEL DATA	1- Collect				

-Processes, outputs, outcomes -Satisfaction, quality improvement	2- Store				
	3- Evaluate				
	4-XXX				
	5-XXX				
6- DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION	<i>i.e.</i> 1- Activities to promote participation/organization of the implementation				

ANNEX II. PLAN-DO-STUDY-ACT (PDSA) OR DEMING SYSTEMATIC PROCESS METHOD

The use of structured Plan-Do-Study-Act (PDSA) cycles and collaborative procedures facilitates the implementation and continuous improvement of health interventions.

Compared to traditional research methodologies in health care, the PDSA cycle offers a science-based and practice-based approach for testing changes in complex systems.

The four stages Plan-Do-Study-Act involve the experimental scientific method: formulating hypotheses, collecting data to test them, analyzing and interpreting the results, and using that information to iterate the hypothesis.

The pragmatic principles of PDSA cycles encourage an iterative approach to intervention appraisal. It allows rapid assessment and offers flexibility to adapt C4D good practice based on collected comments and feedback, ensuring the development of fit-for-purpose solutions.

The PDSA cycle enables the results of a test to be forecast and then measured over time, quantitatively or qualitatively, to assess the outcome of an intervention along its process or outcomes of concern.

Given the complexity of different conditions with many inherent elements, measuring data over time helps to understand the natural variation in a system, increases awareness of other factors influencing processes or outcomes, and provides insight into the impact of an intervention.

Like any scientific approach, it is important to document each stage of the PDSA cycle to support technical soundness, quality, reflection and team learning. This ensures that the necessary knowledge is acquired to support organizational development and transfer to other environments.

The PDSA method includes the following steps (Figure 1):

- ✓ **PLAN:** In this step, all the actions required to implement VL BP and to test the changes are planned. It describes the actors involved (who), the assigned roles and functions (what), the time frame (when) and the scenario where it will take place (where).
- ✓ **DO:** In this step, testing of the planned action is carried out. Once completed, data are collected and any unexpected problems or observations that arise during the process are documented.
- ✓ **STUDY:** In this step, the data obtained during the test (DO) are analysed. The results obtained are compared with those estimated beforehand. The knowledge gained from the results is recapitulated.
- ✓ **ACT:** Based on the lessons learned in the previous steps, adjustments are made to the implemented plan. Necessary modifications are made to improve the process or intervention. Once improved, this change is implemented in a new PDSA cycle.

Figure 1. PDSA cycle

The steps for C4D are detailed as follows:

Step 1 (PLAN) includes Phase I (Intensive care) and Phase II (Aftercare) and the general objectives are:

- To define C4D participants recruitment strategy.
- To define C4D multidisciplinary teams that will implement and monitor the BP.
- To define C4D other preparatory activities (design and management of the platforms and protocols for their management, data management, etc.), with specific focus to sustainability supporting activities.

Step 2 (DO) includes Phase I (Intensive care) and Phase II (Aftercare) and the general objectives are:

- To manage the data in the Digital Platforms.
- To describe actions implemented, including deviations from those planned.
- To describe any deviation from the planned actions.
- To describe any problems.
- To describe unexpected findings.

Step 3 (STUDY) includes Phase I (Intensive care) and Phase II (Aftercare) and the general objectives are:

- To analyse the measured results.
- To compare the results obtained with predictions.
- To compile lessons learned.
- To obtain unintended consequences, surprises, successes and failures.

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Step 4 (ACT) This implies the introduction of the lesson learned elements from previous steps (Plan-DO-Study) to consecutive interventions, meaning round2 with group B, that includes Phase I (Intensive care) and Phase II (Aftercare):

- To include modifications on the previous PLAN Intensive care if required
- To include modifications on the PLAN Aftercare
- To define sustainability based on the approach designed.

ANNEX III. SQUIRE

The SQUIRE guidelines provide a framework for reporting new knowledge about how to improve healthcare including quality, safety, and value of healthcare. It uses methods to establish that observed outcomes were due to the intervention(s).

Table 1 reflects the topics to be described and the related tasks to be developed during the implementation of the intervention, where most of the information would be reflecting the correspondent activities that would feed part of the evaluation reports.

Ciplinary teams

Table 1. Tasks planned to be developed during the evaluation of data after implementation o the BP.

Introduction	Why did you start?	Reference
1. Problem/ Challenge Description	Nature and significance of the local problem/Challenge	Task 5.1
2. Available Knowledge	Summary of what is currently known about the problem, including relevant previous studies	Task 5.1
3. Rationale	Informal or formal frameworks, models, concepts, and/or theories used to explain the problem, any reasons or assumptions that were used to develop the intervention(s), and reasons why the intervention(s) was expected to work	Task 5.1
4. Specific Aims	Purpose of the project and of this report “General purpose of the intervention” of the scope definition template “Objectives” of the collaborative methodology	Task 5.1
Methods	What did you do?	

5. Context	Contextual elements considered important at the outset of introducing the intervention(s)	Task 5.1
6. Intervention(s)	Description of the intervention(s) in sufficient detail that others could reproduce it	<u>Template</u> Step 1 task 5.2
	b. Specifics of the team involved in the work	<u>Template</u> Step 1 task 5.2
7. Study of the Intervention(s)	a. Approach chosen for assessing the impact of the intervention(s)	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Approach used to establish whether the observed outcomes were due to the intervention(s)	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
8. Measures	a. Measures chosen for studying processes and outcomes of the intervention(s), including rationale for choosing them, their operational definitions, and their validity and reliability	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Description of the approach to the ongoing assessment of contextual elements that contributed to the success, failure, efficiency, and cost	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	c. Methods employed for assessing completeness and accuracy of data	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
9. Chronogram	Expected timing of the activities of the Change package, scheduling the start and end month	<u>Template</u> Step 1 task 5.2
10. Analysis	a. Qualitative and quantitative methods used to draw inferences from the data	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Methods for understanding variation within the data, including the effects of time as a variable	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
11. Ethical Considerations	Ethical aspects of implementing and studying the intervention(s) and how they were addressed, including, but not limited to, formal ethics review and potential conflict(s) of interest	Study Protocol
Results	What did you find?	

11. Results	a. Initial steps of the intervention(s) and their evolution over time (e.g., time-line diagram, flow chart, or table), including modifications made to the intervention during the project	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Details of the process measures and outcome	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	c. Contextual elements that interacted with the intervention(s)	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	d. Observed associations between outcomes, interventions, and relevant contextual elements	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	e. Unintended consequences such as unexpected benefits, problems, failures, or costs associated with the intervention(s).	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	f. Details about missing data	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
Discussion	What does it mean?	
14. Summary	a. Key findings, including relevance to the rationale and specific aims	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Particular strengths of the project	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
15. Interpretation	a. Nature of the association between the intervention(s) and the outcomes	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Comparison of results with findings from other publications	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	c. Impact of the project on people and systems	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	d. Reasons for any differences between observed and anticipated outcomes, including the influence of context	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	e. Costs and strategic trade-offs, including opportunity costs	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
16. Limitations	a. Limits to the generalizability of the work	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	b. Factors that might have limited internal validity such as confounding, bias, or imprecision in the design, methods, measurement, or analysis	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2
	c. Efforts made to minimize and adjust for limitations	<u>Template</u> Step 3 task 5.2

17. Conclusions	a. Usefulness of the work	WP4
	b. Sustainability	WP4
	c. Potential for spread to other contexts	WP4
	d. Implications for practice and for further study in the field	WP4
	e. Suggested next steps	WP4
Other Information		
18. Funding	Sources of funding that supported this work. Role, if any, of the funding organization in the design, implementation, interpretation, and reporting	Grant Agreement: 80% EU+20% particular source

ANNEX IV. CONSOLIDATED FRAMEWORK FOR IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH CONSTRUCTS (CFIR)

Implementation studies are supported by this methodology developed in previous EU project Chrodis +.

The CFIR provides a menu of constructs that have been associated with effective implementation. The Updated CFIR builds on the 2009 version that included constructs from a range of 19 frameworks or related theories including Everett Rogers' Diffusion of Innovations Theory and Greenhalgh and colleagues' compilation based on their review of 500 published sources across 13 scientific disciplines. The CFIR considered the spectrum of construct terminology and definitions and compiled them into one organizing framework. The 2022 Updated CFIR draws on more recent literature and feedback from users.

The constructs are conceptual elements described in the table below. They are described in scales according to their **Relevance** in a scale of 10 points where: 0 = not relevant at all and 10 = very relevant. For this purpose, relevance is defined as: How significant, valued, or necessary the variable has been in the Local Good Practice implementation. They also describe the **influence** in a 5 points Likert Scale (Very positive/Positive/Neutral/Negative/Very negative) according to **reasoning** explanation behind the scores for their relevance and influence.

Table 1 shows the different constructs and their description to be used in C4D.

Table 1. Constructs of the CFIR methodology.

Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research Constructs		
<u>CFIR Website</u>		
Construct	Short Description	
I. INTERVENTION CHARACTERISTICS		
A	Intervention Source	Perception of key stakeholders about whether the intervention is external or internally developed.
B	Evidence Strength & Quality	Stakeholders' perceptions of the quality and validity of evidence supporting the belief that the intervention will have desired outcomes.
C	Relative Advantage	Stakeholders' perception of the advantage of implementing the intervention versus an alternative solution.
D	Adaptability	The degree to which an intervention can be adapted, tailored, refined, or reinvented to meet local needs.
E	Trialability	The ability to test the intervention on a small scale in the organization, and to be able to reverse course (undo implementation) if warranted.
F	Complexity	Perceived difficulty of implementation, reflected by duration, scope, radicalness, disruptiveness, centrality, and intricacy and number of steps required to implement.
G	Design Quality & Packaging	Perceived excellence in how the intervention is bundled, presented, and assembled.
H	Cost	Costs of the intervention and costs associated with implementing the intervention including investment, supply, and opportunity costs.
II. OUTER SETTING		
A	Patient Needs & Resources	The extent to which patient needs, as well as barriers and facilitators to meet those needs, are accurately known and prioritized by the organization.
B	Cosmopolitanism	The degree to which an organization is networked with other external organizations.
C	Peer Pressure	Mimetic or competitive pressure to implement an intervention; typically because most or other key peer or competing organizations have already implemented or are in a bid for a competitive edge.
D	External Policy & Incentives	A broad construct that includes external strategies to spread interventions, including policy and regulations (governmental or other central entity), external mandates, recommendations and guidelines, pay-for-performance, collaboratives, and public or benchmark reporting.

III. INNER SETTING		
A	Structural Characteristics	The social architecture, age, maturity, and size of an organization.
B	Networks & Communications	The nature and quality of webs of social networks and the nature and quality of formal and informal communications within an organization.
C	Culture	Norms, values, and basic assumptions of a given organization.
D	Implementation Climate	The absorptive capacity for change, shared receptivity of involved individuals to an intervention, and the extent to which use of that intervention will be rewarded, supported, and expected within their organization.
1	Tension for Change	The degree to which stakeholders perceive the current situation as intolerable or needing change.
2	Compatibility	The degree of tangible fit between meaning and values attached to the intervention by involved individuals, how those align with individuals' own norms, values, and perceived risks and needs, and how the intervention fits with existing workflows and systems.
3	Relative Priority	Individuals' shared perception of the importance of the implementation within the organization.
4	Organizational Incentives & Rewards	Extrinsic incentives such as goal-sharing awards, performance reviews, promotions, and raises in salary, and less tangible incentives such as increased stature or respect.
5	Goals and Feedback	The degree to which goals are clearly communicated, acted upon, and fed back to staff, and alignment of that feedback with goals.
6	Learning Climate	A climate in which: a) leaders express their own fallibility and need for team members' assistance and input; b) team members feel that they are essential, valued, and knowledgeable partners in the change process; c) individuals feel psychologically safe to try new methods; and d) there is sufficient time and space for reflective thinking and evaluation.
E	Readiness for Implementation	Tangible and immediate indicators of organizational commitment to its decision to implement an intervention.
1	Leadership Engagement	Commitment, involvement, and accountability of leaders and managers with the implementation.
2	Available Resources	The level of resources dedicated for implementation and on-going operations, including money, training, education, physical space, and time.
3	Access to Knowledge & Information	Ease of access to digestible information and knowledge about the intervention and how to incorporate it into work tasks.
IV. CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIVIDUALS		
A	Knowledge & Beliefs about the Intervention	Individuals' attitudes toward and value placed on the intervention as well as familiarity with facts, truths, and principles related to the intervention.

B	Self-efficacy	Individual belief in their own capabilities to execute courses of action to achieve implementation goals.
C	Individual Stage of Change	Characterization of the phase an individual is in, as he or she progresses toward skilled, enthusiastic, and sustained use of the intervention.
D	Individual Identification with Organization	A broad construct related to how individuals perceive the organization, and their relationship and degree of commitment with that organization.
E	Other Personal Attributes	A broad construct to include other personal traits such as tolerance of ambiguity, intellectual ability, motivation, values, competence, capacity, and learning style.
V. PROCESS		
A	Planning	The degree to which a scheme or method of behavior and tasks for implementing an intervention are developed in advance, and the quality of those schemes or methods.
B	Engaging	Attracting and involving appropriate individuals in the implementation and use of the intervention through a combined strategy of social marketing, education, role modelling, training, and other similar activities.
1	Opinion Leaders	Individuals in an organization who have formal or informal influence on the attitudes and beliefs of their colleagues with respect to implementing the intervention.
2	Formally Appointed Internal Implementation Leaders	Individuals from within the organization who have been formally appointed with responsibility for implementing an intervention as coordinator, project manager, team leader, or other similar role.
3	Champions	“Individuals who dedicate themselves to supporting, marketing, and ‘driving through’ an [implementation]” [101] (p. 182), overcoming indifference or resistance that the intervention may provoke in an organization.
4	External Change Agents	Individuals who are affiliated with an outside entity who formally influence or facilitate intervention decisions in a desirable direction.
C	Executing	Carrying out or accomplishing the implementation according to plan.
D	Reflecting & Evaluating	Quantitative and qualitative feedback about the progress and quality of implementation accompanied with regular personal and team debriefing about progress and experience.

Framework Guidance:

The CFIR is intended to be used to collect data from individuals who have power and/or influence over implementation outcomes. See the CFIR Outcomes Addendum for guidance on identifying these individuals and selecting outcomes.

The CFIR must be fully operationalized prior to use in a project:

- 1) Define the subject of each domain for the project (see guidance for each domain below).
- 2) Replace broad construct language with project-specific language if needed.
- 3) Add constructs to capture salient themes not included in the updated CFIR.

I. INNOVATION DOMAIN

Innovation: The “thing” being implemented, e.g., a new clinical treatment, educational program, or city service.

[Document the innovation being implemented, e.g., innovation type, innovation core vs. adaptable components, using a published reporting guideline. Distinguish the innovation (the “thing” that continues when implementation is complete) from the implementation process and strategies used to implement the innovation (activities that end after implementation is complete).]

Construct Name	Construct Definition <i>The degree to which:</i>
A. Innovation Source	The group that developed and/or visibly sponsored use of the innovation is reputable, credible, and/or trustable.
B. Innovation Evidence-Base	The innovation has robust evidence supporting its effectiveness.
C. Innovation Relative Advantage	The innovation is better than other available innovations or current practice.
D. Innovation Adaptability	The innovation can be modified, tailored, or refined to fit local context or needs.
E. Innovation Trialability	The innovation can be tested or piloted on a small scale and undone.
F. Innovation Complexity	The innovation is complicated, which may be reflected by its scope and/or the nature and number of connections and steps.
G. Innovation Design	The innovation is well designed and packaged, including how it is assembled, bundled, and presented.
H. Innovation Cost	The innovation purchase and operating costs are affordable.

II. OUTER SETTING DOMAIN

Outer Setting: The setting in which the Inner Setting exists, e.g., hospital system, school district, state. There may be multiple Outer Settings and/or multiple levels within the Outer Setting (e.g., community, system, state).

Project Outer Setting(s): [Document the actual Outer Setting in the project, e.g., type, location, and the boundary between the Outer Setting and the Inner Setting.]

Construct Name	Construct Definition The degree to which:
A. Critical Incidents	Large-scale and/or unanticipated events disrupt implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.

B. Local Attitudes	Sociocultural values (e.g., shared responsibility in helping recipients) and beliefs (e.g., convictions about the worthiness of recipients) encourage the Outer Setting to support implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
C. Local Conditions	atti
D. Partnerships & Connections	The Inner Setting is networked with external entities, including referral networks, academic affiliations, and professional organization networks.
E. Policies & Laws	Legislation, regulations, professional group guidelines and recommendations, or accreditation standards support implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
F. Financing	Funding from external entities (e.g., grants, reimbursement) is available to implement and/or deliver the innovation.
G. External Pressure	External pressures drive implementation and/or delivery of the innovation. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to External Pressures that are not included in the sub constructs below.
1. Societal Pressure	Mass media campaigns, advocacy groups, or social movements or protests drive implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
2. Market Pressure	Competing with and/or imitating peer entities drives implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
3. Performance-Measurement Pressure	Quality or benchmarking metrics or established service goals drive implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
III. INNER SETTING DOMAIN	
Inner Setting: The setting in which the innovation is implemented, e.g., hospital, school, city. There may be multiple Inner Settings and/or multiple levels within the Inner Setting, e.g., unit, classroom, team.	
Project Inner Setting(s): [Document the actual Inner Setting in the project, e.g., type, location, and the boundary between the Outer Setting and the Inner Setting.]	
Construct Name	Construct Definition
	The degree to which:
<i>Note:</i>	<i>Constructs A – D exist in the Inner Setting regardless of implementation and/or delivery of the innovation, i.e., they are persistent general characteristics of the Inner Setting.</i>
A. Structural Characteristics	Infrastructure components support functional performance of the Inner Setting. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Structural Characteristics that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Physical Infrastructure	Layout and configuration of space and other tangible material features support functional performance of the Inner Setting.
2. Information Technology Infrastructure	Technological systems for tele-communication, electronic documentation, and data storage, management, reporting, and analysis support functional performance of the Inner Setting.
3. Work Infrastructure	Organization of tasks and responsibilities within and between individuals and teams, and general staffing levels, support functional performance of the Inner Setting.

B. Relational Connections	There are high quality formal and informal relationships, networks, and teams within and across Inner Setting boundaries (e.g., structural, professional).
C. Communications	There are high quality formal and informal information sharing practices within and across Inner Setting boundaries (e.g., structural, professional).
D. Culture	There are shared values, beliefs, and norms across the Inner Setting. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Culture that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Human Equality-Centeredness	There are shared values, beliefs, and norms about the inherent equal worth and value of all human beings.
2. Recipient-Centeredness	There are shared values, beliefs, and norms around caring, supporting, and addressing the needs and welfare of recipients.
3. Deliverer-Centeredness	There are shared values, beliefs, and norms around caring, supporting, and addressing the needs and welfare of deliverers.
4. Learning-Centeredness	There are shared values, beliefs, and norms around psychological safety, continual improvement, and using data to inform practice.
<i>Note:</i>	<i>Constructs E – K are specific to the implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.</i>
E. Tension for Change	The current situation is intolerable and needs to change.
F. Compatibility	The innovation fits with workflows, systems, and processes.
G. Relative Priority	Implementing and delivering the innovation is important compared to other initiatives.
H. Incentive Systems	Tangible and/or intangible incentives and rewards and/or disincentives and punishments support implementation and delivery of the innovation.
I. Mission Alignment	Implementing and delivering the innovation is in line with the overarching commitment, purpose, or goals in the Inner Setting.
J. Available Resources	Resources are available to implement and deliver the innovation. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Available Resources that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Funding	Funding is available to implement and deliver the innovation.
2. Space	Physical space is available to implement and deliver the innovation.
3. Materials & Equipment	Supplies are available to implement and deliver the innovation.
K. Access to Knowledge & Information	Guidance and/or training is accessible to implement and deliver the innovation.
IV. INDIVIDUALS DOMAIN	
Individuals: The roles and characteristics of individuals.	

ROLES SUBDOMAIN	
Project Roles: [Document the roles applicable to the project and their location in the Inner or Outer Setting.]	
Construct Name	Construct Definition
A. High-level Leaders	Individuals with a high level of authority, including key decision-makers, executive leaders, or directors.
B. Mid-level Leaders	Individuals with a moderate level of authority, including leaders supervised by a high-level leader and who supervise others.
C. Opinion Leaders	Individuals with informal influence on the attitudes and behaviors of others.
D. Implementation Facilitators	Individuals with subject matter expertise who assist, coach, or support implementation.
E. Implementation Leads	Individuals who lead efforts to implement the innovation.
F. Implementation Team Members	Individuals who collaborate with and support the Implementation Leads to implement the innovation, ideally including Innovation Deliverers and Recipients.
G. Other Implementation Support	Individuals who support the Implementation Leads and/or Implementation Team Members to implement the innovation.
H. Innovation Deliverers	Individuals who are directly or indirectly delivering the innovation.
I. Innovation Recipients	Individuals who are directly or indirectly receiving the innovation.
CHARACTERISTICS SUBDOMAIN	
Project Characteristics: [Document the characteristics applicable to the roles in the project based on the COM-B system or role-specific theories.]	
Construct Name	Construct Definition: The degree to which:
A. Need	The individual(s) has deficits related to survival, well-being, or personal fulfillment, which will be addressed by implementation and/or delivery of the innovation.
B. Capability	The individual(s) has interpersonal competence, knowledge, and skills to fulfill Role.
C. Opportunity	The individual(s) has availability, scope, and power to fulfill Role.
D. Motivation	The individual(s) is committed to fulfilling Role.
V. IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS DOMAIN	
Implementation Process: The activities and strategies used to implement the innovation.	
Project Implementation Process: [Document the implementation process framework and/or activities and strategies being used to implement the innovation. Distinguish the implementation process used to implement the innovation (activities that end after implementation is complete) from the innovation (the “thing” that continues when implementation is complete).]	
Construct Name	Construct Definition: The degree to which individuals:

A. Teaming	Join together, intentionally coordinating and collaborating on interdependent tasks, to implement the innovation.
B. Assessing Needs	Collect information about priorities, preferences, and needs of people. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Assessing Needs that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Innovation Deliverers	Collect information about the priorities, preferences, and needs of deliverers to guide implementation and delivery of the innovation.
2. Innovation Recipients	Collect information about the priorities, preferences, and needs of recipients to guide implementation and delivery of the innovation.
C. Assessing Context	Collect information to identify and appraise barriers and facilitators to implementation and delivery of the innovation.
D. Planning	Identify roles and responsibilities, outline specific steps and milestones, and define goals and measures for implementation success in advance.
E. Tailoring Strategies	Choose and operationalize implementation strategies to address barriers, leverage facilitators, and fit context.
F. Engaging	Attract and encourage participation in implementation and/or the innovation. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Engaging that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Innovation Deliverers	Attract and encourage deliverers to serve on the implementation team and/or to deliver the innovation.
2. Innovation Recipients	Attract and encourage recipients to serve on the implementation team and/or participate in the innovation.
G. Doing	Implement in small steps, tests, or cycles of change to trial and cumulatively optimize delivery of the innovation.
H. Reflecting & Evaluating	Collect and discuss quantitative and qualitative information about the success of implementation. Note: Use this construct to capture themes related to Reflecting & Evaluating that are not included in the subconstructs below.
1. Implementation	Collect and discuss quantitative and qualitative information about the success of implementation.
2. Innovation	Collect and discuss quantitative and qualitative information about the success of the innovation.
I. Adapting	Modify the innovation and/or the Inner Setting for optimal fit and integration into work processes.
CFIR OUTCOMES ADDENDUM	
I. ANTECEDENT ASSESSMENTS	
Name	Definition
A. Acceptability	The extent to which an innovation is perceived as “agreeable, palatable, or satisfactory” (Proctor, 2009).
B. Appropriateness	The “perceived fit, relevance, or compatibility of the innovation [...] for a given practice setting, provider, or consumer; and/or perceived fit of the innovation to address a particular issue or problem” (Proctor, 2009).
C. Feasibility	The extent to which an innovation “can be successfully used or carried out within a given agency or setting” (Proctor, 2009).
D. Implementation Climate	The extent to which the Inner Setting has an implementation climate.
E. Implementation Readiness	The extent to which the Inner Setting is ready for implementation.

II. IMPLEMENTATION OUTCOMES	
Name	Definition
A. Anticipated Implementation Outcomes	Outcomes based on perceptions or measures of the likelihood of future implementation success or failure, i.e., implementation outcomes that have not yet occurred. These outcomes are forward-looking; constellations of CFIR determinants across domains predict these outcomes.
1. Adoptability	The likelihood key decision-makers will decide to put the innovation in place/innovation deliverers will decide to deliver to innovation.
2. Implementability	The likelihood the innovation will be put in place or delivered.
3. Sustainability	The likelihood the innovation will be put in place or delivered over the long-term.
B. Actual Implementaiton Outcomes	Outcomes based on perceptions or measures of current (or past) implementation success or failure, i.e., implementation outcomes that have occurred. These outcomes are backward-looking; constellations of CFIR determinants across domains explain these outcomes.
1. Adoption	The extent key decision-makers decide to put the innovation in place/innovation deliverers decide to deliver the innovation.
2. Implementation	The extent the innovation is in place or being delivered.
3. Sustainment	The extent the innovation is in place or being delivered over the long-term.
III. INNOVATION OUTCOMES	Outcomes that capture the success or failure of the innovation, based on the impact of the innovation on three important constituents: Innovation Recipients, Innovation Deliverers, and Key Decision-Makers. Impact is defined by: Reach ("The absolute number, proportion, and representativeness of individuals who are willing to participate in a given initiative, intervention, or program.") x Innovation Effectiveness ("The impact of an intervention on important outcomes, including potential negative effects, quality of life, and economic outcomes.")
Name	Definition
A. Innovation Recipient Impact	Recipient Reach x Innovation Effectiveness
B. Innovation Deliverer Impact	Deliverer Reach x Innovation Effectiveness
C. Key-Decision Maker (or System) Impact	Key-Decision Maker Reach x Innovation Effectiveness